

FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OF SÃO PAULO

INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

PROFESSIONAL POSTGRADUATE PROGRAM IN TECHNOLOGICAL
INNOVATION

**INNOVATIVE MOBILE APPLICATION FOR
ASSESSING BLINKING AND EYELID MOVEMENTS**

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São José dos Campos - SP

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I dedicate this work to my beloved wife, Daniela, and my daughter, Laura, whose unwavering support and endless love have been my greatest strength. Their encouragement has been invaluable. I also deeply thank my esteemed advisors, Dr. Regina Célia Coelho, Dr. Tammy Hentona Osaki, and Dr. Carlos Marcelo Gurjão de Godoy, for their invaluable guidance and wisdom throughout this journey.

“Innovation is the outcome of a habit, not a random act.”

Sukant Ratnakar

RESUMO

O ato de piscar, ou seja, de abrir e fechar as pálpebras dos olhos, é um reflexo fisiológico importante para a saúde ocular. Contudo, o ato de piscar pode ficar alterado em várias condições, como na síndrome do olho seco e após cirurgias palpebrais. Sabe-se pouco sobre alterações nos parâmetros do piscar nessas condições, incluindo mudanças na duração, frequência e amplitude. Os métodos atuais para avaliar objetivamente os parâmetros do piscar são complexos e, muitas vezes, inadequados para a prática clínica cotidiana. Além disso, é necessário um software especializado para analisar imagens e identificar com precisão os olhos, avaliando seu estado de abertura. Por outro lado, ferramentas disponíveis comercialmente, como câmeras ou telefones celulares, podem facilitar a captura de imagens dos olhos que poderiam ajudar nesse processo. Assim, o objetivo deste trabalho foi desenvolver um aplicativo para dispositivos móveis capaz de realizar, em tempo real, análises quantitativas acuradas do piscar e gerar insights estatísticos. O software foi criado utilizando o framework multiplataforma Flutter juntamente com ferramentas de aprendizado de máquina. Os resultados mostram que o aplicativo móvel fornece medições objetivas e reproduzíveis, permitindo um melhor monitoramento de doenças palpebrais e uma melhor compreensão dos resultados cirúrgicos. Esta ferramenta representa um avanço significativo na oftalmologia digital, auxiliando profissionais de saúde em seu trabalho diário no diagnóstico e acompanhamento do tratamento oftalmológico.

Palavras-chave: piscar; movimento palpebral; olho seco; aplicativo móvel; inteligência artificial.

ABSTRACT

The act of blinking, that is, the act of closing and opening the eyelids, is a physiological reflex action necessary for ocular health. However, blinking is altered in several conditions, such as dry eye syndrome and after eyelid surgery, and little is known about the duration, frequency, and amplitude changes in eyelid movements. Current methods to objectively assess blinking parameters are complex and often unsuitable for everyday clinical practice. Also, specialized software is required to analyze images, accurately identify eyes, and assess their opening status. On the other hand, commercially available tools, such as cameras or mobile phones, can facilitate the capture of eye images, thereby aiding this process. Thus, the objective of the present work was to develop a mobile device app capable of performing real-time, quantitative, and accurate analysis of blinking and generating statistical insights. The software was developed using the Flutter cross-platform framework and machine learning tools. The results show that the mobile application provides objective, repeatable measurements, enabling better monitoring of eyelid diseases and a better understanding of surgical outcomes. This tool represents a significant advancement in digital ophthalmology, supporting healthcare professionals in their daily work in diagnosis and treatment follow-up.

Keywords: blinking; eyelid movement; dry eye; mobile application; artificial intelligence.

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List of Abbreviations

AI – Artificial Intelligence
ANVISA – Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária
API – Application Programming Interface
BApp – Blink Application
BPM – Blinks Per Minute
CNN – Convolutional Neural Network
EAR – Eye Aspect Ratio
EPM – Escola Paulista de Medicina
FPS – Frames Per Second
HCI – Human-Computer Interface
IBI – Inter-Blink Interval
ICT – Institute of Science and Technology
IDE – Integrated Development Environment
LGPD – Lei Geral de Proteção de Dados (General Data Protection Law)
LPS – Levator Palpebrae Superioris
ML – Machine Learning
OOM – Orbicularis Oculi Muscle
PEOU – Perceived Ease of Use
PU – Perceived Usefulness
QUIS – Questionnaire for User Interaction Satisfaction
RMSE – Root Mean Square Error
SaMD – Software as a Medical Device
SBR – Spontaneous Blink Rate
SUS – Sistema Único de Saúde (Unified Health System)
TAM – Technology Acceptance Model
TIC – Information and Communication Technology (Tecnologia da Informação e Comunicação)
UNIFESP – Universidade Federal de São Paulo
UX – User Experience

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Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

This chapter establishes the context and motivations for this study, presents the objectives, and describes the document's structure.

1.1 Context

Eye blinking is a rapid motor act of eyelid closure and reopening that serves multiple functions essential for maintaining eye health and enhancing visual processing [1]. Spontaneous blinking, in particular, is an unconscious and brief eyelid closure that is crucial not only for maintaining ocular surface health but also for ensuring visual clarity by distributing the tear film [2]. The vital role of blinking becomes evident in patients who are unable to perform this function: the lack of eyelid closure rapidly leads to severe exposure-related damage that may culminate in irreversible vision loss. This highlights the need for precise, objective tools to evaluate blink dynamics, given their direct impact on ocular integrity and visual outcomes [2]. Proper eyelid blinking is imperative for visual function, for the distribution of the tear film over the ocular surface, and for tear drainage. Blinking can be altered in conditions such as dry eye syndrome, eyelid ptosis, and following eyelid surgeries, compromising ocular health [2–4]. The estimated prevalence of ptosis, encompassing both congenital and acquired forms, ranges from 0.79 to 1.99 per 10,000 individuals [5].

While the prevalence of these conditions is well documented, little is known about alterations in blinking parameters in dry eye syndrome and after eyelid surgeries.

Current methods for assessing blinking objectively remain complex and impractical for clinical use or patient self-monitoring.

Automated, quantitative diagnostic tools have been increasingly developed to support clinicians by facilitating early detection and intervention for various ocular and neurological conditions. These technologies streamline diagnostic workflows by providing standardized, reproducible data and reducing reliance on subjective clinical impressions. Moreover, they enhance clinical decision-making by offering standardized, reproducible assessments that minimize inter-observer variability. Mobile and AI-based solutions, in particular, have shown the potential to democratize access to advanced diagnostic capabilities, enabling real-time evaluations in diverse clinical and even home-based settings [6–12]. By integrating machine learning algorithms with imaging and sensor technologies, these tools can identify subtle pathological changes that may not be evident through conventional examination methods, thereby improving diagnostic accuracy, treatment monitoring, and patient outcomes.

Without accessible and objective tools, clinical evaluation of eyelid movement remains subjective, delaying diagnosis and impairing treatment monitoring.

1.2 Motivation

The Department of Ophthalmology and Visual Sciences at the Paulista School of Medicine, Federal University of São Paulo (EPM/UNIFESP), has been developing automated tools to assess blink rates in patients with several conditions.

The initial process used by EPM/UNIFESP researchers involved cameras recording eyelid movements. Then, in a two-step process, custom software processes the resulting videos to generate the blink rate information [13–19].

To streamline the process, collaborative research has been initiated between EPM/UNIFESP and the Institute of Science and Technology, Federal University of São Paulo (ICT/UNIFESP), to develop new approaches. The initial outcome of this collaboration was a study aimed at developing a smartphone application to objectively measure the frequency of eyelid movements [20].

The previously developed application relies on a server to process videos and extract blink rate information. This work developed an application that performs video analysis locally, uploading only the analysis results to the server. This approach reduces costs and increases accessibility, facilitating broader adoption by both doctors and patients.

1.3 Objectives

Primary objective: To develop an innovative mobile application capable of assessing eyelid movement by recording the opening and closing of the eyes over time, using only on-device processing without needing external equipment or server infrastructure.

Specific objectives:

- Develop a mobile application that analyzes the frequency and amplitude of these movements in real time using the device's built-in camera and pre-recorded videos.
- Conduct the analysis using the mobile application in an integrated and real-time manner.
- To design and apply a blink classification algorithm capable of distinguishing between partial and complete blinks, improving precision over traditional threshold models.
- Address how the mobile application can assist in evaluating blinking changes in patients with dry eyes and those undergoing eyelid surgeries.
- To validate the system against public datasets and through clinical use in collaboration with ophthalmologists.
- Develop cross-platform mobile applications for Android and iOS, enabling virtually anyone with a smartphone to objectively analyze eyelid movements, ensuring broad accessibility and usability in clinical and personal contexts.
- To integrate an innovative Doctor Mode that allows healthcare professionals to register patients, manage blink data, and export structured data (e.g., Excel) for clinical decision-making.

- To contribute to technological innovation in digital ophthalmology by delivering a portable, efficient, and reproducible tool for dynamic eyelid analysis.

Finally, it is essential to define that the primary target audience for this application comprises ophthalmologists and oculoplastic surgeons. The tool supports these specialists in clinical settings by providing objective metrics to complement subjective examinations. Secondly, the application serves patients who require home-based monitoring under medical supervision.

1.4 Text structure

This dissertation is organized as follows: Chapter 2 presents the literature review, identifying the scientific understanding of the subject, knowledge gaps, and opportunities. Chapter 3 outlines the dissertation proposal guiding this study. Chapter 4 details the results. Chapter 5 provides the conclusions and outlines the next steps.

Chapter 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter introduces this research's fundamental concepts and provides the necessary context to understand its objectives and findings.

2.1 Eye conditions

Eye conditions are a crucial area of medical research and clinical practice due to their substantial impact on vision and overall quality of life. This section provides an overview of several conditions, including dermatochalasis, ptosis, and dry eye syndrome.

2.1.1 Dermatochalasis

Dermatochalasis is characterized by excess skin and sagging tissue around the eyelids, typically due to aging or the loss of skin elasticity. Blepharoplasty is a surgical procedure that enhances the aesthetic appearance of the eyelid region. It involves excision and removal of skin and fat pads. It requires a comprehensive preoperative evaluation (including medical and ophthalmic history and detailed examination), addressing preexisting dry eye symptoms, brow position, eyelid ptosis, lower eyelid position, and cheek projection, with standard approaches for skin-only upper blepharoplasty and conservative fat excision or repositioning for the lower eyelid [21,22].

2.1.2 Eyelid Ptosis

Upper eyelid ptosis, characterized by the drooping of the upper eyelid, can be categorized as minimal (1–2 mm), moderate (3–4 mm), or severe (>4 mm), potentially obscuring the pupil completely. This condition may affect one or both eyes and can be present congenitally or acquired later in life. Although ptosis typically manifests in isolation, it can be associated with various conditions such as degenerative, neurological, myogenic, hereditary disorders, and tumors. In addition to the characteristic drooping, patients with ptosis often report symptoms such as a tired appearance, blurred vision, and reduced superior visual field [23]. Treatment is surgical in most cases. The estimated prevalence of ptosis, encompassing both congenital and acquired forms, ranges from 0.79 to 1.99 per 10,000 individuals [5].

Figure 2.1 depicts a patient with right-sided ptosis.

Figure 2.1: Patient with right-sided ptosis. From: [24]

2.1.3 Dry eye syndrome

Dry eye is a multifactorial ocular surface disease characterized by the loss of tear film homeostasis and accompanied by ocular symptoms. Tear film instability, hyperosmolarity, inflammation, ocular surface damage, and neurosensory abnormalities play important etiological roles. Symptoms include eye itching, ocular hyperemia, discomfort, and transient changes in visual acuity. Treatment involves using ocular lubricants and, when necessary, other medications and behavioral

measures [4]. Prolonged exposure to digital devices and computer screens exacerbates dryness [25]. Early detection of dry eye syndrome prevents discomfort and visual impairment. Prompt diagnosis allows timely management and treatment to maintain eye health [26].

2.2 Eyelid dynamics and analysis

Blinking is a rapid movement of the eyelid that closes and opens the palpebral fissure. The intrinsic speed of this action imposes significant technical constraints on measurement systems, as a complete blink can finish in less than 100 msec [2]. This duration dictates the required temporal resolution for accurate detection. Drawing upon the Nyquist-Shannon sampling theorem, which mandates that the sampling rate must exceed twice the maximum frequency (bandwidth) present in the signal, an event occurring over 100 msec requires a minimum sampling frequency greater than 20 Frames Per Second (FPS) [27]. This physiological constraint provides the formal, theoretical basis for the developed application's goal of operating at 25 FPS, ensuring that the software captures sufficient temporal data to reliably detect and quantify critical blink parameters, thereby avoiding signal loss or aliasing.

There are three types of blinking: spontaneous, which occurs without an evident external stimulus; reflex, in response to a tactile, optical, or auditory stimulus; and voluntary, which is consciously controlled. Physiologically, the blinking motion is performed by a pair of antagonistic muscles: the orbicularis oculi muscle (OOM) is responsible for eyelid closure, while the levator palpebrae superioris (LPS) muscle opens it. The proper functioning of these structures is fundamental, as surgeries such as ptosis correction and blepharoplasty may directly act on them [2].

The quality of the movement can be described by its kinetics. The linear relationship between the amplitude of a blink and its maximum velocity is known as the "main sequence" and serves as an indicator of motor neuron activity. The characterization of a normal blink includes several parameters. The Spontaneous Blink Rate (SBR) in healthy adults stabilizes at 10-20 blinks per minute. The Inter-Blink Interval (IBI),

however, is not fixed, and its distribution is an individual characteristic, which justifies the need for more detailed analyses than a simple average. Regarding the amplitude, blinks can be classified as "twitches" (almost imperceptible), incomplete, or complete. In healthy individuals, most blinks are complete enough to cover the pupil's center, a crucial factor for adequate lubrication [2].

Proper eyelid blinking is imperative for visual function, for the distribution of the tear film over the ocular surface, and for tear drainage. Blinking can be altered in several conditions, such as dry eye syndrome and after eyelid surgery. Blinking alterations can cause disturbances of the ocular surface and tear drainage [3].

It is essential to better understand the blinking alterations associated with dry eye syndrome and how eyelid surgeries and eyelid conditions affect blinking.

The objective investigation of eyelid movements requires methods to capture images of the patient's face and submit them to specialized software analysis to recognize and quantify eyelid movements [15,18,20,28]. Image capture can be performed using external cameras [18,28] or even the cameras present on mobile devices [15,20]. Specialized software, like MATLAB, can perform subsequent analysis to detect eyelid movement [18]. Analysis is also performed by applications hosted on web pages that mobile devices or desktops can access [20]. In conjunction with MATLAB, custom software developed by specialized companies, such as Visage Technologies, is also employed to analyze eyelid movements [28].

The most common process for analyzing eyelid movements involves two stages: 1) external cameras for image capture and 2) software for subsequent analysis on desktops [18,28]. Figure 2.2 depicts this process.

2.2.1 Mobile Application

Few integrated mobile application options are available for objectively analyzing eyelid movements. The DryEyeRhythm mobile device app addresses the increasing prevalence of undiagnosed dry eye disease (DED) caused by digital device use and aging by collecting data. The project was executed under a consignment contract with Juntendo University Graduate School of Medicine and InnoJin Inc., Tokyo. To ensure professional technical implementation, the application development was outsourced to the software companies OHAKO Inc. and Medical Logue Inc. Furthermore, the

research received funding and support from major ophthalmic and contact lens manufacturers, such as SEED Co., Ltd., Alcon Japan, Ltd., and HOYA Corporation. Figure 2.3 illustrates that it is freely accessible on Apple's App Store and Google Play [29].

Figure 2.2: Two-stage analysis. Own work.

Figure 2.3: DryEyeRhythm app in Google Play. Own work.

The EyeScore mobile application, developed at the Department of Clinical Research, Westview Eye Institute in San Diego, CA, USA, uses blink rate and patterns as early clinical biomarkers for dry eye disease (DED). Motivated by the need for a low-cost,

patient-centered solution to address early diagnosis challenges, the app was designed as a Point-of-Care (POC) mHealth tool. Technically, it employs facial landmarks and Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR) algorithms on 1-minute video recordings to detect full and partial blinks. Furthermore, it generates a unique 10-point 'Eye Healthiness Score' by combining objective data with subjective risk factors, such as age, gender, and contact lens use. Although designed for the iOS platform, it remains unavailable for download [30]. Figure 2.4 depicts screenshots of the user interface for the EyeScore application. In summary, the current literature presents solutions that are either limited to real-time screening, such as DryEyeRhythm, or focused solely on processing fixed-length recorded videos, such as EyeScore. No single mobile tool currently integrates both capabilities to offer flexibility for both clinical consultation (real-time) and retrospective analysis (pre-recorded). This gap highlights the need for a hybrid solution.

2.3 Software tools

Integrating software tools into academic research has significantly transformed various fields, enabling researchers to enhance the accuracy, efficiency, and scope of their studies. This section examines the software tools employed in the current academic work, detailing their functionalities, applications, and contributions to the research objectives.

2.3.1 Flutter

Flutter is a free, open-source mobile application development framework that enables development from a single codebase across mobile, web, and desktop platforms [31]. It supports development on Linux, macOS, ChromeOS, and Windows [31]. Rather than replacing native iOS and Android applications, Flutter offers an innovative approach to application development. Developers can create applications entirely with Flutter or embed them into existing native applications [31]. This flexibility allows incorporating native iOS and Android code when necessary, overcoming framework-specific limitations on native functionality, and streamlining app development while reducing production costs and complexity across platforms.

Figure 2.4: EyeScore app. From [30].

Flutter is powered by Dart, an object-oriented, class-defined, garbage-collected language that can be compiled ahead of time (AOT) into native 32-bit and 64-bit ARM code for iOS and Android [31,32]. It offers a rich set of widgets that implement both Material Design and iOS styles to create modern applications optimized for mobile environments. Designing applications using these widgets is akin to designing with HTML.

The camera module within the Flutter framework has been integrated to capture real-time images from the device's camera, fully leveraging the underlying platform's capabilities [33].

Flutter supports the development of internationalized applications by providing localization mechanisms [34]. These mechanisms allow developers to manage translations and locale-specific resources and dynamically adjust content based on the user's language and regional settings.

Flutter's selection is crucial because it directly supports the main goal of creating a portable, efficient, and reproducible application. By using a single codebase for both Android and iOS, Flutter significantly enhances the application's accessibility and reach, covering nearly the entire smartphone user base. This accessibility is essential for gaining broader adoption by both doctors and patients, including within large public health services. Additionally, its native support for localization is vital for reaching a

diverse audience and ensuring the application works across multiple languages, such as Portuguese, English, and Spanish.

2.3.2 Google ML Kit

ML Kit is a comprehensive suite of machine-learning tools developed by Google. It was initially introduced in 2018 in close integration with Firebase. Today, developers can seamlessly incorporate machine learning features into Android and iOS applications using the new standalone ML Kit SDK version. This toolkit supports the development process for both native and cross-platform applications [35].

It integrates on-device machine learning into applications to address real-world problems. ML Kit's Vision and Natural Language APIs allow developers to solve everyday challenges or create new user experiences. These free tools are powered by Google's machine-learning models [36].

ML Kit's APIs operate on-device, facilitating real-time applications such as processing live camera streams and ensuring the functionality remains accessible offline [36].

Google ML Kit's face detection API detects faces in an image, identifies key facial features, and delineates their contour [37]. As ML Kit supports real-time face detection, we can leverage it in our application to assess eyelid movements.

Research has utilized Google's ML Kit face detection API for applications such as identifying dyslexia and driver drowsiness, demonstrating its effectiveness and accuracy [38,39].

Google ML Kit is the core technology that enables real-time, on-device assessment of eyelid movement without requiring external equipment or server infrastructure. Using ML Kit, the system performs local facial detection and calculates metrics such as the Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR) and eye openness probability. This ability for objective, real-time, dynamic eyelid analysis directly supports the project's aim of advancing technological innovation in digital ophthalmology. Focusing on on-device processing helps reduce costs and enhances accessibility, promoting broader adoption.

2.3.3 Firebase

Firebase is a platform developed by Google to support mobile and web application development. It offers various tools and services to streamline development, improve app quality, and increase user engagement.

Firebase Firestore is a NoSQL database, meaning it does not rely on the traditional relational model based on fixed schemas and tables. Instead, it stores data in flexible, schemaless structures, such as documents and collections, allowing greater scalability and adaptability to evolving application requirements. This database enables real-time data synchronization, allows developers to handle complex data structures efficiently and supports both online and offline data access, ensuring data availability under varying network conditions [40].

Firebase Authentication provides a range of methods for verifying user identities. It supports email and password login, social media logins (Google and Facebook), and anonymous authentication. This service helps developers securely manage and integrate user authentication into their applications [41].

Firebase Storage offers solutions for storing and serving user-generated content, including photos, videos, and other files [42]. It integrates with Firebase Authentication for secure access and includes tools for managing files and metadata. This service supports scalable data storage to accommodate growing storage needs.

These Firebase components enable developers to build and maintain robust applications by leveraging Google's infrastructure and capabilities [43,44].

Firebase provides the critical infrastructure necessary to ensure the security, integrity, and regulatory compliance of the application, which functions as a Software as a Medical Device (SaMD). The use of Firebase Authentication is essential for implementing the Doctor Mode, allowing healthcare professionals to register patients and manage clinical data under strict access control, which is necessary when handling sensitive patient data. Furthermore, implementing cloud backups via Firebase Storage mitigates the risk of data loss associated with local data (Hive database and output videos), ensuring compliance with data security requirements, particularly the Brazilian General Data Protection Law (LGPD).

2.3.4 Figma

Figma is a collaborative interface design tool that allows designers to work on projects together. It enables the design of web and application interfaces, as well as the creation of visual interfaces and wireframes. Designers use vector tools for illustration and prototype and software development tools for hand-off. The platform supports real-time collaboration, permitting multiple team members to log into and modify a design project simultaneously. Designers create reusable components, design systems, and style guides to ensure consistency. The platform also provides access to a library of templates, themes, plugins, and UI kits [45–47].

Using Figma is essential for creating a highly usable and intuitive Human-Computer Interface (HCI), especially for specialized clinical users operating in Doctor Mode. The resulting interface design lays the foundation for future work in the dissertation, particularly the formal evaluation of user acceptance using established frameworks such as the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (which assesses Perceived Ease of Use and Usefulness) and the Questionnaire for User Interaction Satisfaction (QUIS). Therefore, Figma helps ensure that the application is not only technologically functional but also designed for clinical acceptance and effective professional use.

2.3.5 Hive

Hive functions as a NoSQL database solution suited for Flutter applications. It operates in Dart, eliminating the need for native code dependencies and ensuring integration with the Flutter framework. The database supports synchronous and asynchronous operations, allowing flexible data handling and storage solutions. It stores complex data types and nested objects, which helps manage the diverse data structures in mobile applications. Additionally, Hive provides an API (Application Programming Interface) for CRUD (Create, Read, Update, and Delete) operations, making it accessible for developers of all skill levels. Its compatibility with Flutter's reactive programming model further enhances its utility, enabling real-time updates and smooth user experiences. Using Hive, Flutter developers can build scalable applications with minimal overhead and maximum performance [48].

Hive is essential for enabling the application's functionality as a clinical monitoring and data management tool. It guarantees local data persistence by storing the raw output predictions from Google ML Kit (such as eye-openness probabilities and EAR) for each analyzed frame. This persistence allows the application to keep a complete analysis history and supports the key goal of Doctor Mode: exporting structured data (e.g., Excel) for detailed clinical decision-making and patient follow-up over time. Without Hive, the analysis data would be temporary and medically unusable.

2.4 Systematic literature review

This section summarizes a systematic literature review conducted by the author as part of a master's degree program. The review investigates state-of-the-art automatic methods for assessing altered eyelid movements caused by ophthalmological conditions such as blepharospasms, facial dystonias, or dry eye syndrome. The complete text of this systematic review was submitted for publication as a preprint [49] and is included in APPENDIX A.

The review identified the dominance of image analysis in the extraction of eyelid-related parameters. The image used to analyze eyelid movements appears in 20 of the 31 selected studies. After image acquisition, machine learning is the predominant technique for extracting eyelid parameters. Recently, mobile applications have facilitated the study of eyelid movements, enabling single-step analyses and broadening accessibility. Blink frequency remains the most widely used parameter for eyelid movement analysis, and cameras are the most common sensors for capturing these movements.

Chapter 3

METHODOLOGY

This chapter details the methodology adopted for this study and presents the expected results.

3.1 Research question

Integrating mobile applications into clinical practice offers unprecedented opportunities for the real-time monitoring and management of various medical conditions. This research explores how a mobile application to evaluate eyelid movement can help understand how eyelid surgeries, such as ptosis repair and blepharoplasties, and eye and eyelid conditions affect blinking. By leveraging technology to deliver objective, continuous, and accurate assessments, such an application has the potential to significantly improve patient outcomes, facilitate early intervention, and streamline healthcare professionals' workflows. This study addresses the efficacy, reliability, and practical implications of using mobile technology to manage these conditions.

The research question is:

How can a mobile application that evaluates eyelid movement assist in evaluating blinking?

3.2 Methodology

The proposed system consists essentially of a mobile application, the Blink application (Bapp), designed to perform the blinking assessment in a single integrated stage, incorporating real-time image capture and analysis. This work builds upon a previous project, "Mobile App for Assessing Hemifacial Spasm Treatment Response Using Machine Learning," which developed Python software and employed machine learning techniques to analyze eyelid movement [20]. That application operates by accessing a web page, with all processing conducted on the server side.

The methodological choices for the BApp were directly driven by its target audience: medical specialists in ophthalmology. Unlike general wellness apps, this tool requires robust data-handling capabilities to fit into a clinical workflow. Consequently, features such as the 'Doctor Mode' (for managing multiple patient records), local data security, and raw data export (for statistical analysis) were prioritized.

In the present work, the mobile application goes further and relies on the Flutter cross-platform framework. It enables the development of Android and iOS mobile operating system applications, covering virtually the entire smartphone user base [50]. The application supports three languages — Portuguese, English, and Spanish — using Flutter's localization library, enabling a broad and diverse audience.

GitHub serves as the code repository for this project, facilitating version control [51]. The platform supports tracking changes, branch management, and code merging. Its extensive use within the developer community offers access to numerous resources and community support, making it an appropriate choice for managing the project's codebase.

Visual Studio Code is the Integrated Development Environment (IDE) for Flutter development [52,53]. This IDE supports Dart and Flutter via multiple extensions, which facilitate coding, debugging, and testing.

Utilizing Firebase Authentication and Firebase Storage in this application ensures controlled user access and efficient data management [41,42]. Firebase Authentication verifies user identities, restricting application access to authorized users. Firebase Storage handles user data storage, including media and files, and integrates with

Firestore Authentication to secure access to that data. This integration facilitates routine cloud backups, preventing the loss of local database information.

Figma is used to prototype user interfaces, allowing users to create detailed, interactive prototypes that replicate the user experience [45]. The process includes designing interface elements, arranging them into coherent layouts, and establishing interactive pathways to simulate user interactions. Figma facilitates development, bridging the gap between initial design concepts and final implementation.

The selected architectural framework for guiding app development is clean architecture, which yields advantages such as improved maintainability, reduced complexity, streamlined codebase modifications, and the creation of robust, easily upgradable, and verifiable applications [54,55]. Such a framework enhances software quality and adaptability to evolving requirements and technological advancements.

The Flutter platform allows integration with the device's camera, which is essential for the App's objective. The captured images undergo real-time analysis without storing the video for subsequent processing. Thus, the analysis result is immediately available after image capture, fulfilling the objective of performing an integrated analysis without subsequent image processing. Figure 3.1 depicts the real-time analysis flowchart.

Figure 3.1: Real-Time Analysis Flowchart. Own work.

Analysis can be performed using either the front or back camera, and camera selection is available on the "New Analysis" page, as shown in Figure 3.2. The zoom and exposure levels also adjust on the screen.

To address the limitations identified in the literature, the BApp was architected with a dual-mode engine. Our application supports both real-time analysis using the device's camera and the processing of pre-recorded videos imported from the gallery. This versatility allows the ophthalmologist to perform immediate bedside assessments or analyze patient-submitted videos for telemedicine purposes.

Figure 3.2: New Analysis page. Own work.

Image capture and eyelid movement evaluation are performed simultaneously, without post-processing. Data are stored locally on the smartphone, enabling effective and objective monitoring while also allowing assessment of the evolution over time of eyelid movement parameters recorded by the application. In addition, the application supports analysis in both real time and with pre-recorded videos, ensuring flexibility across different clinical and research scenarios.

The selected local database is Hive, a NoSQL database solution tailored for local storage requirements in a Flutter application [48]. Hive offers integration with Flutter and furnishes a robust API for data storage and retrieval. This feature set renders it suitable for managing modest to moderate datasets within applications.

The Hive database supports storing unstructured information in JSON format. The application stores data and time information, duration, and an array containing information from each frame within an AnalysisEntity for each analysis. Consequently,

the FrameEntity serves as a sub-entity of the analysis entity, with each frame storing the frame number, date and time, and the detected probability of eye-opening.

An analysis lasting 30 seconds is conducted at 25 frames per second, generating a total of 750 frames (30 x 25). To facilitate real-time analysis, each frame must be displayed at 40 milliseconds (1/25). During this time window, the application must capture an image with the camera, perform eye-state detection, and store information for each frame.

Analyzing eyelid opening states occurs using the Google ML Kit, a Computer Vision Application Programming Interface (API) developed by Google [36]. A comparison with other machine learning tools reveals the suitability of the Google ML Kit's face detection results. Optimized for mobile devices, ML Kit conducts all processing locally on the device. Specifically, the Google ML Kit module for this task is Face Detection, which detects eye contours and other facial features to recognize the state of eyelid opening.

The Google ML Kit receives an image as input and conducts face detection. The framework can detect multiple faces within a single image. However, the application only considers the first detected face, assuming the app will analyze the user individually. After face detection, the framework proceeds to classify the eye status. This classification provides a probability value indicating the degree of openness for each eye.

Google ML Kit can identify specific facial contours, including the eyes, nose, and mouth. As face contour detection is activated, it provides a list of points outlining the shape of each detected facial feature. Figure 3.3 illustrates the mapping of these points onto a facial structure.

The application's blink detection performance was evaluated against Eyeblink8 [56], a reference database containing annotated blink frames considered the gold standard.

The app enables the analysis of pre-recorded video files. As depicted in Figure 3.4, this process occurs in stages. In the first stage, the video is split into frames and stored in a temporary directory for later processing.

Each stored frame is loaded in the second stage for analysis of the eye-opening state. Google ML Kit attempts to detect a face in the image. Once a face is detected,

facial feature data is extracted. If the algorithm fails to detect a face, it skips that frame and attempts to detect one in the next.

Figure 3.3: Face contour detection by Google ML Kit. From [37].

In the final stage, the data stored in this vector is written to a local database and made available for further analysis in the Analysis History screen, together with the real-time analysis.

This study involves the collaboration of Dr. Tammy Hentona Osaki, Adjunct Professor in the Department of Ophthalmology and Visual Sciences, and Dr. Midori Osaki, both from EPM/UNIFESP. They use the application to objectively assess blinking in their patients, as they have previously collaborated with advisor Regina Célia Coelho and co-advisor Carlos Marcelo Gurjão de Godoy [20].

The study assesses normal blinking and changes in blinking parameters in patients undergoing ptosis repair and blepharoplasty (to assess potential post-surgical

changes in blinking). Recruited patients are from the outpatient clinic of the Oculoplastic Division in the Department of Ophthalmology at UNIFESP.

Figure 3.4: Pre-recorded video analysis sequence. Own work.

This project is part of a broader project already approved by the UNIFESP Ethics Committee (CEP/UNIFESP CAAE 80417524.2.0000.5505).

3.2.1 Eye Blink Detection Dataset

The Eyeblick8 [56] and Talking Face [57] are the two public eyeblick detection datasets used to validate the pre-recorded video analysis feature. The Eyeblick8 dataset contains over 82,600 frames and 408 blinks. It includes natural facial movements, expressions, and other intensive non-blink motions. The Talking Face dataset comprises 5,000 frames, corresponding to approximately 200 seconds of recording, capturing a subject engaged in a natural conversation with another person. The video recording uses a static camera to model facial behavior during the interaction. The dataset includes 61 additional blinks, bringing the total annotated blinks to 469.

It is important to emphasize that these public datasets were originally designed for general computer vision research rather than clinical ophthalmology. Consequently, they exclusively contain video sequences of healthy individuals with no known ocular or neurological pathologies. Therefore, the algorithm was not tested on pathological cases within the scope of these specific datasets.

Despite the absence of clinical conditions, these datasets provide significant data plurality. They capture a wide range of spontaneous facial behaviors, including natural head movements, varied facial expressions, and intense non-blinking. This diversity challenges the algorithm's robustness against geometric noise and varying poses, providing a solid baseline for detecting physiological blinking before applying the tool to clinical scenarios.

The annotations for each video are in two files: the first lists the frame numbers and their acquisition times, while the second contains manually annotated eye states.

Each row in the annotation file contains the following information: Frame ID, Blink ID, NF, LE_FC, LE_NV, RE_FC, RE_NV.

In the annotation files, the value X represents the default or neutral state, indicating normal visibility and frontal orientation, whereas a change to N denotes a negative condition, such as loss of frontal face orientation or lack of eye visibility.

- Frame ID: Frame counter. This sequential number starts at zero and increments by 1 with each frame.
- Blink ID: A unique blink ID; the eye blink interval definition occurs as a sequence of frames with the same blink ID. When a blink is not detected, the value -1 is shown, and when a blink is detected, the number of blink sequences is shown. The first blink is 1, the second blink is 2, and so on.
- No frontal face (NF): This variable indicates whether the subject's face is oriented toward the camera. The default value X denotes a frontal face orientation, meaning the face is clearly visible and aligned with the camera. When the subject turns the head sideways, or the face is no longer frontal, the value changes from X to N, indicating the absence of a frontal face. In such cases, reliable eyeblink detection may be compromised due to partial facial visibility or changes in eye appearance.
- Left eye (LE), right eye (RE), face (F)
- Eye fully closed (FC): If the subject's eyes are closed from 90% to 100%, the flag changes from X to C.

- Eye not visible (NV): While the subject's eye is not visible because of the hand, bad light conditions, hair, or even too fast head movement, this variable changes from X to N.

Table 3.1 shows the annotated reference for the first blink from the Talking Face video. It identifies the beginning of the blink in frame 168 and the end in frame 176. The Blink_ID indicates the detected blink number. The first blink, number 1, occurs between frames 168 and 176. The LE_FC stands for “Left Eye Fully Closed,” indicating that the left eye is closed from 90% to 100%. Between frames 170 and 171, the left eye is fully closed. The RE_FC stands for “Right Eye Fully Closed.” Between frames 170 and 171, the right eye is also fully closed.

Table 3.1: Annotated frames for the first blink in the Talking Face video.

Frame_ID	Blink_ID	NFF	LE_FC	LE_NV	RE_FC	RE_NV
166	-1	X	X	X	X	X
167	-1	X	X	X	X	X
168	1	X	X	X	X	X
169	1	X	X	X	X	X
170	1	X	C	X	C	X
171	1	X	C	X	C	X
172	1	X	X	X	X	X
173	1	X	X	X	X	X
174	1	X	X	X	X	X
175	1	X	X	X	X	X
176	1	X	X	X	X	X
177	-1	X	X	X	X	X

Figure 3.5 shows the chart of the probability of openness for both eyes, predicted by Google ML Kit, for the first blink in the Talking Face video.

Figure 3.5: Eye openness probability for both eyes predicted by Google ML Kit for the first blink in the Talking Face video. Own work.

3.2.2 Eye Blink Detection Algorithm

The interpretation of raw data from Google ML Kit detects the frames where a blink occurred. The first approach to detecting eye blinks involved defining a blink as a period when the probability of eye openness drops below 0.5, where “0.0” represents “totally closed eye” and “1.0” represents “totally opened eye”. Figure 3.6 illustrates a problem with this method: When the probability bounces around probability 0.5 - falling below 0.5, rising above 0.5, and then falling again below 0.5 - the algorithm counts two blinks, which is incorrect, as only one blink or no blink would have happened.

Figure 3.6: Illustration of the problem of eye openness probability chart with two frames below probability 0.5. Own work.

Using a single threshold to detect a blink is not a practical solution. To address the limitations of single-threshold models, a novel multi-threshold logic was developed

specifically for this study. Unlike existing methods in the literature that typically rely on a binary open/closed classification or geometric Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR) alone, this approach introduces a three-tier probability model to distinguish between partial and complete blinks. Figure 3.7 shows these thresholds.

Figure 3.7: Illustration of probability charts with thresholds that indicate the beginning and ending of both partial or complete blinks. Own work.

The specific values for these thresholds (0.75, 0.25, and 0.98) were established through an iterative heuristic calibration process. We analyzed frame-by-frame probability outputs from a diverse training set of video recordings, correlating the numerical probability drops with visual confirmation of eyelid positions.

- 0.75 (Blink Onset/Partial): Testing revealed that during the initial phase of a blink or a partial blink, the eye-openness probability consistently drops below 0.75 but often stays above 0.25.
- 0.25 (Complete Closure): Analysis showed that fully closed eyes (complete blinks) reliably produce probability scores below 0.25, effectively filtering out incomplete movements.
- 0.98 (Recovery): To prevent false positives from micro-fluctuations (noise) during the reopening phase, the system requires the probability to return to a high confidence level of 0.98 to confirm the blink cycle is finished.

This specific threshold configuration enables the algorithm to dynamically categorize blink type.

The pseudocode for eye-blink detection is shown in Figure 3.8.

```
BEGIN

  DEFINE partial_blink_detected AS FALSE
  DEFINE full_blink_detected AS FALSE

  IF eye_open_probability < 0.75 THEN
    IDENTIFY partial_blink
    SET partial_blink_detected TO TRUE
  END IF

  IF eye_open_probability < 0.25 THEN
    IDENTIFY full_blink
    SET full_blink_detected TO TRUE
  END IF

  IF eye_open_probability > 0.98 AND
    (partial_blink_detected OR full_blink_detected) THEN
    END blink
    SET partial_blink_detected TO FALSE
    SET full_blink_detected TO FALSE
  END IF

END
```

Figure 3.8: Pseudocode for blink detection algorithm. Own work.

Figure 3.9(a) illustrates an instance of a partial blink, where the eye openness probability decreases below 0.75 but remains above the 0.25 threshold, which characterizes a complete blink. The blink is considered complete when the eye-openness probability returns to 0.98. Figure 3.9(b) shows a complete blink when the eye-openness probability drops below 0.25.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3.9: Illustration of probability charts of partial blink (a) and complete blink (b). Own work.

In addition to probability thresholds, the algorithm incorporates a temporal consistency check to mitigate noise inherent in image capture, such as lighting fluctuations or camera instability that might produce outlier frames. To distinguish a genuine blink from a single-frame anomaly (false positive), the system analyzes the neighborhood of consecutive frames.

A configuration parameter, `consecutiveClosedForBlink`, was set to 1, indicating that a blink must persist for at least 2 consecutive frames to be registered. Consequently, isolated detection events lasting only a single frame (approx. 40ms at 25 FPS) are automatically rejected as noise. This smoothing technique ensures that momentary dips in probability caused by sensor noise do not trigger false blink counts, requiring temporal confirmation to validate the eyelid movement.

To enhance the accuracy of blink detection, particularly in discerning partial blinks, the application uses the Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR) [58]. The EAR is a quantitative scalar value used to characterize the openness of the eye based on 2D facial landmarks. It is calculated as the ratio of the vertical distance between the eyelids to the horizontal distance between the eye corners.

Mathematically, if we consider six facial landmarks for each eye (P_1 to P_6), where P_1 and P_4 represent the eye corners, and the remaining points represent the upper and lower eyelids, the EAR is calculated as follows:

$$EAR = \frac{||P_2 - P_6|| + ||P_3 - P_5||}{2 \times ||P_1 - P_4||} \quad (1)$$

Under normal conditions, when the eye is open, the EAR remains relatively constant. However, as the eyelids close during a blink, the vertical distance approaches zero, leading to a significant drop in the EAR value. This geometric behavior provides a robust signal for blink onset and completion, independent of lighting variations that might affect probability-based models.

3.2.3 Validation

The app processes videos from the EyeBlink8 and Talking Face public datasets to validate its ability to detect blinks. The system considers the eye blink detected if any intersection occurs between the detected blink and the annotation. The intersection interval with the ground truth is counted only once as a True Positive. The results are exported to Excel spreadsheets and compared using the root mean square error (RMSE). The results were normalized using the StandardScaler function and evaluated using the 'mean_squared_error' metric from Scikit-Learn [59].

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=0}^n (y - \hat{y})^2} \quad (2)$$

where \hat{y} is a vector containing the predicted values, and y is the ground truth value for each analyzed value. The variable n represents the total number of values (samples) considered in the evaluation, and i is the index of each sample in the summation. The result is the root of the difference between the predicted and the ground truth values divided by the number of values (value represented by n).

To compare the results to other papers using the same datasets, we used the following equations:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad (3)$$

$$Recall(TP \text{ rate}) = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (4)$$

$$FP \text{ rate} = \frac{FP}{N} \quad (5)$$

$$MA = \frac{TP+TN}{P+N} \quad (6)$$

where TP is True Positive (the eye blinks are annotated in the reference dataset and were predicted by the app), FP is False Positive (when the app predicts the eye blink, but it is not found in the annotated dataset), FN is False Negative (when an eye blink

is annotated in the dataset but not predicted by the app). N is the total number of frames in the video dataset. P is the number of frames with eye blinks (positives), while $N-P$ corresponds to the number of frames with open eyes (negatives). TN is the True Negative, calculated by subtracting the TP , FP , and FN frames from the total number of frames. MA is the mean accuracy. TN is the True Negative, calculated by subtracting the TP , FP , and FN frames from the total number of frames of the videos. P is calculated by subtracting the total number of frames from N .

Chapter 4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter reports the results achieved in this study.

4.1 Firebase Integration

Some features of this project were implemented using Google Firebase cloud infrastructure. Firebase provides authentication, requiring users to log in with a Google account to access the application's features. Employing Firebase Authentication is preferable to implementing an in-house login system due to its robust security measures, comprehensive support for various authentication methods, and seamless integration with other Firebase services, collectively enhancing development efficiency and the user experience. Figure 4.1 shows the Login screen with a Google Sign-In button.

Figure 4.1: Login screen with a Google Sign-In button. Own work.

The dialog box shown in Figure 4.2 indicates that the user must log in to access the feature. This box appears when the user tries to access a feature before completing the login process.

Figure 4.2: Dialog indicating that login is required to access the feature. Own work.

The backup feature also uses the Firestore structure. The application employs Hive, a local database, to save patient and analysis information. To reduce the risk of data loss in the event of a device issue, the application can save a copy of the current data from Hive and the output videos to Firestore Storage.

The system stores the backup as comma-separated values files. One file contains all the patient's data; another contains all the analysis data except the frame analysis; and

a file with the frame information for each analysis is created. Figure 4.3 depicts the directory structure that keeps backup files in Firebase Firestore. Each user has access only to their backup files, and the directory structure uses the `user_id` as the security role to keep user information segregated and safe. Only authenticated users can access the information.

Figure 4.3: Firebase storage directory structure displaying backup files. Own work.

4.2 Internationalization of APP

Since its inception, the application has addressed internationalization issues. Thus, it detects the operating system language (iOS or Android) and configures one of three options: English, Spanish, or Portuguese. English is the default language if the selected language is not among these three. Figure 4.4 shows the language selection on iOS devices.

Figure 4.5 shows the main menu in three languages, English, Portuguese, and Spanish, based on the user's language choice context.

4.3 Configurations screen

Figure 4.6 shows the configuration screen. On this screen, the user can turn Debug Mode on or off, which displays additional debugging information. This mode is used during development and hidden in the production version of the application.

The Doctor Mode allows the professional user to record different patients and monitor each patient's analysis. The 4.4 section details that feature.

The following three settings relate to analysis configuration. The resolution configuration specifies the image resolution that the camera captures. The resolution affects the time required to process each frame. A higher resolution results in lower FPS (Frames per Second).

Figure 4.4: Interface for selecting language preferences on iOS devices. Own work.

The Generate Output Video option toggles eye detail generation for each frame. The doctor can use this video for posterior analysis. However, generating this video in real time requires additional processing time, which may reduce the FPS.

The analysis duration option determines the maximum analysis time, ranging from 15 to 120 seconds. The analysis can finish at any time, but it will automatically stop when it reaches maximum duration.

Figure 4.5: Main menu in English, Portuguese, and Spanish versions. Own work.

Figure 4.6: Configurations screen. Own work.

4.4 Doctor Mode

When Doctor Mode is set in the Configurations screen, the Patient item appears in the main menu, as shown in Figure 4.7.

Figure 4.7: Main menu (a) with Doctor Mode off and (b) with Doctor Mode on. Own work.

The Patients option in the Main menu opens the Patients screen, as shown in Figure 4.8. This screen displays a list of cards containing selected information about each patient, including their first and last names, age, and the illness they are experiencing. Each card has a three-dot button that opens a pop-up menu, shown in Figure 4.9, with additional options relevant to the selected patient.

In the Patients screen, the user can add a new patient by tapping the plus button in the upper-right corner of the screen. This action opens a new screen, as depicted in Figure 4.10, that displays a form for entering the patient's information.

Figure 4.8: Patients screen. Own work.

Figure 4.9: Pop-up menu displaying patient context options. Own work.

Starting a new real-time analysis or a new file analysis from the pop-up menu displays a screen where the doctor can add more information about the analysis. Researchers from EPM/UNIFESP have already requested this feature and are currently testing the application. In the form depicted in Figure 4.11, the information regarding whether the analysis is before or after an intervention is specified by the number of days until or after the intervention, along with a text field to enter any observations about the context of that analysis.

<

Add Patient

Name

Surname

Illness

Birth date

Observations

Save

Figure 4.10: Patient data input form for entering patient information. Own work.

<

New real-time analysis

Pre Post

days

15

Observations

Go to analysis

Figure 4.11: Patient's new analysis data input form. Own work.

The delete patient option in the pop-up context menu will delete patient information. A confirmation dialog screen, shown in Figure 4.12, pops up to prevent accidental deletions.

The analysis history filtered by the selected patient is displayed using the view Analysis History option from the pop-up menu. In the Analysis History screen depicted in Figure 4.13, all the patient's analyses are organized in cards containing selected information

such as the date and time of the analysis, the blink rate for each eye, whether the analysis happened before or after the intervention, and the number of days before or after the intervention.

Figure 4.12: Patient delete confirmation dialog to confirm the removal of patient information. Own work.

Figure 4.13: Analysis history screen with a list of cards displaying information about the patient's analysis. Own work.

Tapping an analysis card from the list in the analysis history screen opens the analysis detail screen, as depicted in Figure 4.25.

4.5 Export to Excel

The export to Excel feature saves an analysis's raw data in an Excel sheet. This functionality is valuable for debugging and provides flexibility in viewing data. It also allows sorting, filtering, and performing operations on the raw data to understand the analysis's results better.

As shown in Figure 4.14, this feature is accessed via the Export to Excel button on the Analysis Detail screen.

Figure 4.14: Analysis Detail screen with an "Export to Excel" button located at the bottom.
Own work.

The next step is to select a sharing option from the underlying operating system. Figure 4.15 shows the options for iOS users.

Figure 4.16 shows the exported Excel sheet containing information about the overall analysis and the eye status of each Frame. This information allows the user to work more flexibly with the raw data and possibly gain more insights.

Figure 4.15: Default iOS share screen interface. Own work.

	A	B	C	D	E
1	Patient	Gustavo Bonesso			
2	Analysis type	AnalysisType.realTime			
3	*** Pre/Post Interval	PrePostIntervention.pre			
4	*** Days Pre/Post	15			
5	*** Observations				
6	Duration	4.4 seconds			
7	Number of Blinks	L: 4	R: 4		
8	Blink Frequency	L: 54.1 BPM	R: 54.1 BPM		
9	FPS:	16.0 FPS			
10					
11	***Frame	***Right Eye Oper	***Left Eye Oper	***Right Eye EAI	***Left Eye EAR
12	0	0,99	0,95	0,25	0,26
13	1	0,99	0,95	0,26	0,28
14	2	0,99	0,95	0,25	0,28
15	3	0,99	0,99	0,28	0,28
16	4	0,99	0,95	0,28	0,29
17	5	0,99	0,95	0,26	0,28
18	6	0,99	0,98	0,28	0,28
19	7	0,99	0,95	0,26	0,26
20	8	0,99	0,98	0,26	0,26
21	9	0,99	0,98	0,26	0,29
22	10	0,99	0,95	0,25	0,28
23	11	0,99	0,95	0,26	0,28
24	12	0,90	0,90	0,20	0,23
25	13	0,00	0,04	0,15	0,17

Figure 4.16: Excel sheet displaying raw data from the analysis. Own work.

4.6 Pre-recorded video analysis

The app can process pre-recorded videos, store analysis results in the local Hive database, and present them to the user. Additionally, the results can be exported to Excel.

4.6.1 Pre-Recorded Video Processing

Figure 4.17 illustrates the application interface for pre-recorded video processing. Google ML Kit detects the eyes and generates 16 coordinates for each one, which, in turn, allows drawing an approximate contour of the eye shape. Figure 4.18 shows the application screen that highlights the eye region and outlines the eye contours. Figure 4.18 also depicts a probability graph of the likelihood of the eyes being open over time, with the vertical axis ranging from 0 (0%) to 1 (100%) and the horizontal axis representing the frame number. The vertical black bar in the center of the graph corresponds to the image's highlighted frame.

Figure 4.17: Application interface for pre-recorded video processing. Own work.

Figure 4.18: Eye detection. Own work.

4.6.2 Results of Eyeblink Detection

Figure 4.19 shows a frame sequence from one of the videos used to validate the first blink annotated in the dataset.

Figure 4.19: Frames sequence for the first blink in the Talking Face video. Own work.

Table 4.1 shows the app's predicted and annotated blink counts from the datasets. The preliminary technical success of the mobile application's artificial intelligence methodology was presented at an international conference, demonstrating the application's capability for real-time blink analysis. The accompanying poster, titled "TECNOLOGIA DE INTELIGÊNCIA ARTIFICIAL NA AVALIAÇÃO DO PISCAR EM TEMPO REAL" [APPENDIX C], details the process by which the app detects each ocular openness state, frame by frame, showing the sequence of frames and the corresponding graphical data. This external presentation of results validates the core findings regarding the precision achieved when comparing the app's algorithm outputs with annotated data.

Table 4.1: The number of eye blinks predicted by the app compared to the annotated eye blinks.

Video	Number of Annotated Eyeblinks	Number of Eyeblinks Predicted by the App
EyeBlink8 #1	38	37
EyeBlink8 #2	88	88
EyeBlink8 #3	65	61
EyeBlink8 #4	31	30
EyeBlink8 #5	30	30
EyeBlink8 #6	41	41
EyeBlink8 #7	72	72
EyeBlink8 #8	43	43
Talking Face	61	61
Total	469	463

The RMSE for the dataset-normalized comparison against the app's predictions was 0.0654. Based on the mean RMSE, the model effectively predicted blinks in the reference datasets.

Table 4.2 compares the results from our app to those of other papers using different methods against the same datasets.

Table 4.2: Comparison of the results from our app to those of other papers using different methods against the same datasets.

	Dataset	Precision	Recall	FP rate	Mean accuracy
Divjak & Bischof [60]	Talking	-	95.0%	19.0%	88.0%
Lee et al. [61]	Talking	83.3%	91.2%	-	-
Drutarovsky & Fogelton [56]	Talking	92.2%	96.7%	0.7%	99.0%
Our app	Talking	95.3%	100.0%	0.5%	99.6%
Drutarovsky & Fogelton [56]	EyeBlink8	79.0%	85.3%	0.7%	99.5%
Our app	EyeBlink8	84.3%	98.5%	0.8%	99.2%

The Precision metric of the EyeBlink8 dataset is lower than that of the Talking Face dataset due to a higher number of false positives (FPs). Occasionally, the app predicts partial blinks that do not correspond to any annotated blinks in the dataset. Figure 4.20 illustrates a sequence of frames that the app predicts as a partial blink, which is not annotated in the reference dataset, as the subject is looking down.

Figure 4.20: A sequence of frames showing a False Positive case where the app predicts a partial blink. Own work.

Figure 4.21 shows the eye-openness chart for a false-positive case, in which the app predicts a partial blink. The openness of both the left and right eyes falls below 0.75,

indicating the onset of a partial blink. The blink concludes when the openness rises to 0.98.

Figure 4.21: Eye openness chart for a case of False Positive. Own work.

4.7 Clinical Analysis in Patients with Blepharospasm

To validate the application in a real-world clinical setting, the Bapp was used to objectively assess the response to botulinum toxin treatment in 5 patients with blepharospasm, a focal dystonia, characterized by forced and increased eyelid closure. The detailed methodology for this clinical assessment, including the analysis of two-minute videos recorded before and after treatment, has previously been documented in the literature [62] and is included in [APPENDIX B].

The key outcomes of this clinical validation demonstrate that the application successfully captured the expected clinical improvement in all assessed cases. Specifically, the objective data confirmed that patients spent more time with their eyes open post-treatment, consistent with clinical expectations. For instance, Patient 1's means that the eye-opening probability increased significantly from 0.59 to 0.97 after the intervention.

Table 4.3 summarizes the average eye-opening probabilities, confirming the application's effectiveness in tracking clinical progression.

Table 4.3: Eye openness before and after treatment.

	Eye openness average before treatment	Eye openness average after treatment
Patient 1	0,59	0,97
Patient 2	0,64	0,88
Patient 3	0,56	0,93
Patient 4	0,80	0,90
Patient 5	0,47	0,81

The visual representation of the eye-opening probability graphs (Figure 4.22) further demonstrates the reduction in both frequency and duration of eyelid spasms post-treatment, reinforcing the application's potential as an objective, portable tool for monitoring disease progression and treatment efficacy. This validation underscores Bapp's capability as a streamlined alternative to more resource-intensive analysis methods.

Figure 4.22: Patient 2 analysis data (a) before treatment and (b) after treatment. Own work.

4.8 Real-time analysis

Measuring a movement as fast as a spontaneous blink is inherently challenging, as a complete blink can finish in less than 100 milliseconds, depending on its amplitude [2]. Real-time analysis poses a significant challenge due to the time required for processing. To achieve a 25 frames per second (FPS) analysis, the system must process each frame within 40 milliseconds.

The first attempt to analyze the frames involved detecting the eyes in the image, cropping the eye regions, and submitting the cropped images to a CNN (Convolutional Neural Network) model to predict two classes: eye open and eye closed. This approach involves several time-consuming steps, resulting in low FPS.

Some incremental enhancements improve performance. The first is to convert the raw camera format (NV21 on Android devices and BRGA8888 on iOS devices) to RGB specifically for the eye-cropped area, rather than converting the entire raw image before cropping.

The cropped eye images were then converted to PNG (Portable Network Graphics) format, converted to grayscale, normalized, and saved locally. These images were used to run the CNN model using TensorFlow. All these steps increase processing time and slow performance, resulting in lower FPS.

The Google ML Kit reduced frame processing time and improved FPS. This framework can process the raw image and produce an eye-opening probability in just one step, without requiring any prior steps.

To ensure the application operates efficiently at the target of 25 to 30 FPS, the mobile device must possess adequate processing power, particularly for on-device machine learning tasks. In the clinical tests conducted for this study, iPhone 11 and iPhone 12 models were utilized. These devices consistently maintained the required frame rate and processing speed, validating the feasibility of the real-time analysis approach on modern smartphones.

Figure 4.23 shows the real-time screen. Pressing the green button labeled “Start analysis” initiates a new analysis. The input camera can be either the front camera or the back camera. The zoom level is also adjustable. The red box indicates a detected face, and the green circles indicate that the eyes are open. When the button is pressed

again, the analysis is complete. The button becomes red during the analysis and displays the caption “Stop analysis.” The analysis will also be halted if the maximum analysis time is reached.

Figure 4.23: Real-time analysis screen examples. Own work.

The analysis results are stored in the Hive database. The “Analysis History” screen depicted in Figure 4.24 allows access to all analyses stored in the Hive database.

Figure 4.24: Analysis History Screen. Own work.

Selecting one analysis leads the user to the “Analysis Detail” screen, illustrated in Figure 4.25. This screen displays the information obtained from the analysis, including the date and time it occurred, the total analysis duration, the number of blinks detected by the app, the blink frequency (blinks per minute), and the FPS achieved during the study.

Figure 4.25: Analysis Detail Screen. Own work.

4.9 Eyelid movement analysis

Dynamic eyelid movement analysis based on 2D images extracted from videos enables the temporal assessment of eye openness. The developed mobile application employs a computer vision algorithm to assess the openness of each eye from pre-recorded video frames and stores the results in a database.

The tests achieved 95.3% precision in blink detection using the Talking Face reference dataset and 84.3% with the EyeBlink8 dataset. This difference mainly due to the greater variability of facial movements and head poses in the EyeBlink8 dataset, which leads to more false positives. The precision level achieved by the application on the Talking Face dataset [57] exceeds the 83.3% reported by Lee et al. [61] and the 92.2% reported by Drutarovsky and Fogelton [56]. Additionally, the precision in blink analysis

with the EyeBlink8 dataset surpasses the 79% achieved by Drutarovsky and Fogelton [56].

The recall also exceeds that of previous works. It recalled 100% of the Talking Face dataset and 98.5% of the EyeBlink8 dataset. Divjak & Bischof [60] reported a recall of 95.0% on the Talking Face dataset, while Lee et al. [61] reported 91.2%, and Drutarovsky and Fogelton [56] reported 96.7%. For the Eye-Blink8 dataset, Drutarovsky and Fogelton [56] reported a recall of 85.3%.

These levels of precision and recall allow the application to analyze eyelid movements as an alternative to manually counting blinks, primarily facilitating the monitoring of abnormal eyelid movements.

The analysis infrastructure consists of a single mobile device, enabling a large audience to perform it. Other approaches for analyzing eyelid movements employ desktop computers with specialized software to obtain the same results, as seen in [6–9,11,12].

The author's SLR identified two mobile applications for detecting eye diseases. Fujio and collaborators developed DryEyeRhythm, which enables real-time analysis but lacks the pre-recorded video analysis feature available in our work [63]. Sydney Zhang and Julio Echegoyen developed EyeScore, which includes the pre-recorded video feature but does not permit real-time analysis like ours [30].

4.10 Clinical Validation using Expert-Annotated Patient Videos

The Bapp underwent a rigorous clinical validation process using real patient data, the results of which are detailed in the attached article APPENDIX F. This validation study is also publicly available as a preprint [64]. This study aimed to firmly establish the application's reliability and objectivity in a clinical environment by comparing its automated detections against ground truth established through manual annotation by ophthalmology specialists from EPM-UNIFESP. The validation used 45 raw analysis datasets from 28 individuals. Specialists from EPM-UNIFESP manually reviewed these videos frame by frame, classifying blinks as complete or partial. The detection

algorithm employed a multi-threshold approach (as documented in APPENDIX C), combining the eye openness probability (with thresholds at 0.75 for blink start and 0.25 for complete blink) with the Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR) algorithm to enhance the detection of subtle partial blinks. The system's performance, evaluated using standard metrics, demonstrated high reliability for objective blink detection. The results were: 98.4% Precision, 96.9% Recall (Sensitivity/True Positive Rate), and an Overall Accuracy of 98.3%.

Although publicly available algorithmic validation datasets (such as EyeBlink8 and Talking Face) are not directly comparable with the real clinical data annotated by EPM-UNIFESP specialists used in this validation phase (APPENDIX F), it is crucial to position the Bapp's performance within the existing literature. In prior algorithmic validations of the Bapp, the system achieved 95.3% Precision using the Talking Face dataset and 84.3% using the EyeBlink8 dataset [8,61]. Even in these benchmark datasets, the Bapp's performance already surpassed the precision achieved by other works; specifically, the 95.3% precision attained on the Talking Face dataset was higher than the 83.3% achieved by Lee et al. and the 92.2% achieved by Drutarovsky and Fogelton. Additionally, the 84.3% precision achieved on the EyeBlink8 dataset surpassed the 79% obtained by Drutarovsky and Fogelton. The high levels of precision (98.4%) and recall (96.9%) achieved in the clinical validation using real EPM-UNIFESP data reinforce the application's potential for monitoring eyelid disorders, surpassing those obtained with public datasets.

4.11 Discussion

The features of the mobile application are comparable to those of custom software developed for desktop computers, such as those produced by Osaki, Gameiro, and collaborators [13–18], which sought the same goals as the present work. As the app can effectively evaluate eyelid movements solely on-device, it eliminates the need for external hardware or server-side analysis and supports real-time and pre-recorded video evaluation. It demonstrates strong performance when validated on public datasets, such as EyeBlink8 and Talking Face, with precision and recall comparable

to or exceeding those of other methods, including those developed by Divjak and Bischof [60], Lee et al. [61], and Drutarovsky and Fogelton [56], which investigated the same blinking features.

In addition to demonstrating technical feasibility, these results highlight the practical relevance of on-device processing for eyelid movement analysis. Unlike traditional approaches that require external cameras, desktop computers, or cloud-based processing pipelines, the proposed application integrates image acquisition, analysis, and data storage into a single mobile device. The app introduces a significant practical differential in digital ophthalmology by integrating two typically distinct workflows. While DryEyeRhythm [29,63] is limited to real-time interactions and EyeScore [30] is restricted to processing 1-minute pre-recorded clips, the app provides a unified platform for both. This dual functionality is clinically critical: real-time analysis optimizes the physician's workflow during face-to-face consultations by providing immediate metrics, while the pre-recorded video feature enables analysis of historical data, research videos, or remote patient monitoring files, all on a single device without the need for external servers.

The app introduces significant technological innovation to digital ophthalmology by initially supporting internationalization in English, Portuguese, and Spanish and being compatible across platforms. In contrast, the other apps, such as DryEyeRhythm [29,63] and EyeScore [30], are restricted either by language availability or by functional limitations, such as the absence of real-time or pre-recorded video analysis.

From a usability and accessibility perspective, multilingual support and cross-platform compatibility are particularly relevant for large public health systems, such as those in Brazil and other Latin American countries, where language barriers and heterogeneous device ecosystems often limit the adoption of digital health tools. By addressing these aspects at the design stage, the Bapp advances beyond proof-of-concept implementations and moves toward real-world scalability.

Clinical validation against expert-annotated patient videos provided definitive evidence of the Bapp's reliability in a real-world clinical setting. The study demonstrated 98.4% Precision, 96.9% Recall, and an Overall Accuracy of 98.3%. That performance is comparable to that obtained by other authors [56,60,61].

Beyond aggregate performance metrics, a qualitative analysis of representative cases provided important insights into the behavior of the detection framework. False-positive

detections were mainly associated with camera instability and geometric noise that affected landmark localization, whereas false-negative detections were typically related to extremely subtle, low-amplitude partial blinks. These observations help contextualize the quantitative results and are consistent with known challenges in eyelid movement analysis [30,56,61].

A critical aspect of validating a clinical diagnostic tool is understanding the implications of classification errors—specifically, False Positives (FPs) and False Negatives (FNs)—in the medical context.

False Positives (FPs) occur when the application incorrectly identifies a non-blink event (e.g., downward gaze or camera instability) as a blink. In a clinical setting, a high rate of false positives could lead to an overestimation of the blink rate. For conditions like Blepharospasm or Dry Eye Disease, where increased blinking is a primary symptom, excessive FPs could lead to a false diagnosis of pathology in healthy individuals or mask the efficacy of treatments (e.g., indicating that Botulinum toxin was ineffective when the blink count remained artificially high due to noise).

Conversely, False Negatives (FN) occur when the system fails to detect a genuine eyelid movement. This is particularly common with partial blinks or subtle movements that do not fully close. In the context of Dry Eye Disease (DED) and neurological disorders, partial blinks are often a compensatory mechanism or a specific pathological sign. Therefore, a high rate of FNs would underestimate the severity of the condition, potentially causing the clinician to miss early-stage symptoms.

The integration of the Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR) into our algorithm was specifically designed to reduce False Negatives. By measuring the geometric distance of the eyelids rather than relying solely on probability opacity, the system became sensitive enough to detect these subtle, clinically significant partial blinks, ensuring that the 'compensatory' behaviors of patients are accurately recorded.

These findings are particularly relevant in the context of eyelid disorders, where clinical assessment of blinking is traditionally subjective and dependent on the examiner's experience. The high agreement observed between automated analysis and expert annotations suggests that the application may serve as a complementary tool for objective monitoring, reducing inter-observer variability and enabling quantitative follow-up over time.

Compared to publicly available datasets like EyeBlink8 and Talking Face, the application maintained or improved the performance levels reported in the literature. Notably, the system provided reliable performance even under non-ideal conditions, such as uneven lighting, lower image quality, and slight camera instability, which are common in real-world clinical environments. Although these datasets are not directly comparable to real clinical data due to differences in acquisition protocols and subject behavior, the consistently high recall values suggest that the algorithm is robust in detecting blink events across diverse scenarios. The lower precision seen in the EyeBlink8 dataset is mainly caused by false positives from partial eyelid closures during downward gaze, as shown in Figure 4.20. This behavior highlights a known challenge in eyelid movement analysis and emphasizes the clinical relevance of distinguishing partial from full blinks, rather than considering all closures as equivalent events.

Implementing a multi-threshold blink classification strategy represents a key contribution of this work. By distinguishing between blink onset, partial closure, and full closure, the algorithm mitigates a common limitation of single-threshold approaches, which often overcount blinks when eye-openness probabilities fluctuate near a fixed cutoff. This differentiation is especially important for conditions such as dry eye syndrome and post-surgical eyelid alterations, where incomplete blinking can be more clinically significant than the total blink count.

Taken together, the misdetections observed reflect well-defined boundary conditions of the probability- and EAR-based approach rather than random failures. This behavior reinforces the overall robustness of the proposed system while clarifying the operational limits of automated eyelid movement analysis.

Despite the strengths and promising results of this study, some limitations of the Bapp must be acknowledged. The system's performance is influenced by mobile device hardware characteristics and environmental conditions during image acquisition. Inadequate lighting, camera instability, or non-frontal face positioning may compromise face and eye detection, thereby affecting the accuracy of eyelid movement measurements. In addition, reliance on a pre-trained machine learning model, such as Google ML Kit, limits transparency into feature extraction and may reduce robustness to atypical facial dynamics or non-standard behavioral scenarios. These constraints should be considered when interpreting the results and highlight the importance of

continued refinement of classification strategies and further validation in larger, more diverse clinical populations and real-world settings.

Overall, the results demonstrate that the proposed mobile application provides a viable, accurate, and scalable solution for objective analysis of eyelid movements. By combining real-time processing, detailed blink classification, and clinical-oriented data management features, the Bapp contributes meaningfully to advancing digital ophthalmology and lays the foundation for future studies focused on longitudinal monitoring, user acceptance, and broader clinical deployment.

Chapter 5

CONCLUSION

This chapter presents the BApp's contributions to digital ophthalmology and outlines future steps in usability, regulation, and data security.

5.1 Conclusion

In this work, we presented the development of a mobile application to analyze eyelid movement using standard tools, resulting in objective monitoring of the clinical progression of patients with eyelid diseases and a better understanding of how eyelid surgeries affect blinking. The mobile application developed enables eyelid movement analysis to reach a larger audience, potentially increasing the quantity and quality of objective information between patients and doctors through its portability and accessibility.

The validation results demonstrate that the application can reliably detect and characterize blinking patterns in both controlled datasets and real clinical scenarios, supporting its use as a complementary, objective tool to traditional clinical assessment. This application was designed to perform all stages of eyelid movement analysis directly on the mobile device, integrating image acquisition, processing, and data storage into a single, portable platform suitable for both clinical and research use.

By reducing technical complexity and eliminating the need for external equipment or server-based analysis, the proposed solution lowers barriers to adoption and expands access to objective eyelid movement assessment.

The scientific community acknowledged the relevance of this work to technological innovation in digital ophthalmology. The research presented was honored with the ‘Valênio Peres França’ Award for Best Free Topic at the 32nd CIOP / 11th CIEPO (2025). This recognition, officially documented in [APPENDIX D], represents an external validation of the application's relevance and innovative potential in assessing eyelid movement disorders.

Taken as a whole, we concluded that the Bapp represents a significant step in digital ophthalmology, offering practical, scalable support to healthcare professionals in their daily work by providing objective, reproducible measurements that may enhance clinical diagnosis, monitoring, and treatment follow-up.

5.2 Future work

Another important area for future research is to broaden the validation beyond healthy subjects and the specific focal dystonias examined here. As mentioned in the methodology, existing public datasets like EyeBlink8 and Talking Face include only healthy individuals. Future efforts should focus on systematically collecting and analyzing video datasets that feature patients with various pathological conditions, including severe Dry Eye Disease (DED), Ptosis, and Facial Palsy.

Validating the algorithm against these pathological cases is essential to ensure its robustness in detecting specific kinematic anomalies—such as tremors, asymmetric velocities, or irregular, incomplete closures—that are absent in healthy subjects. Creating a dedicated dataset for these conditions would also fill a significant gap in the current literature.

Building on the results of this study, future work may increasingly focus on aspects of user adoption. An important direction in this context involves the formal evaluation of the user experience (UX) and overall technology acceptance, which may require additional user data collection. Accordingly, future studies may employ validated methodologies, such as the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and the Questionnaire for User Interaction Satisfaction (QUIS) [65,66]. The TAM study may quantitatively measure both Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) and Perceived Usefulness

(PU) of the application. At the same time, the QUIS may evaluate subjective satisfaction with the human-computer interface. Such validation would support broader adoption of the Bapp by healthcare professionals using the Doctor Mode and by patients for effective self-monitoring at home, contributing to the goal of delivering a practical, accessible tool for digital ophthalmology. While the Bapp has demonstrated effectiveness in clinical research and shows potential to support public health services (SUS), transitioning the application to widespread clinical use requires adherence to national and international regulatory standards. A crucial future step is securing formal certification for the application as a Software as a Medical Device (SaMD) for clinical deployment. This process requires compliance with ANVISA's regulatory framework for devices, including classification, notification, and registration requirements detailed in RDC N° 751, of September 15, 2022 [67]. As the app is SaMD, it must also meet the specific regularization criteria defined in RDC N° 657, of March 24, 2022.

Furthermore, for the software life cycle process, the application should ensure rigorous conformance to the international standard IEC 62304, which is part of the required documentation for high-risk SaMD registration [68,69]. Any post-market modifications must follow the alteration procedures stipulated in RDC N° 340 (which is detailed in IN 74/2020) [70]. Finally, given that the application manages sensitive patient data (likely used in the Doctor Mode), robust data security measures are paramount and require compliance with the Brazilian General Data Protection Law (LGPD, Lei n° 13.709, of August 14, 2018) [71]. Achieving this regulatory compliance phase would support the Bapp's safety, quality, and official availability for clinical practice.

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APPENDIX A

Preprints are preliminary reports that have not undergone peer review.
They should not be considered conclusive, used to inform clinical practice,
or referenced by the media as validated information.

Automated Applications for Assessing Abnormal Eyelid Movements: A Systematic Literature Review

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Systematic Review

Keywords: Eyelid movement, Machine learning, Facial dystonia, Dry eye

Posted Date: October 6th, 2025

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-7773892/v1>

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Additional Declarations: The authors declare no competing interests.

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Automated Applications for Assessing Abnormal Eyelid Movements: A Systematic Literature Review

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Abstract**Purpose**

The primary objective of this study is to identify the technology, methods, and tools commonly employed in automated applications for assessing altered eyelid movements.

Methods

This review consulted three databases known for their excellent reputation and technical quality: PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar. The initial search identified 905 papers. Removing duplicates and applying exclusion criteria narrowed the selection to 31 documents for analysis. The search included publications from January 2018 to June 2024 to focus on recent works.

Results

This review identified the dominance of image analysis in extracting eyelid-related parameters. The image used to analyze eyelid movements appears in 20 of the 31 selected studies. After image acquisition, machine learning is the predominant technique for extracting eyelid parameters. Recently, mobile applications have facilitated the study of eyelid movements, enabling single-step analyses and broadening accessibility. Blink frequency remains the most utilized parameter for eyelid movement analysis, and cameras are the most common sensor for capturing these movements.

Conclusion

The analysis identified the most used technology, methods, and tools for analyzing automated applications that assess altered eyelid movements. Specifically, this review shows that image analysis, primarily through machine learning, is vital for evaluating eyelid movements, with blink frequency as the most analyzed parameter. Also, mobile applications have expanded access to these assessments, using cameras as the primary sensor and enabling simpler, single-step analyses.

Keywords

Eyelid movement; Machine learning; Facial dystonia; Dry eye

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Highlights

- The study explores technology, methods, and tools for analyzing eyelid movements.
- Image analysis is dominant in extracting eyelid parameters
- Machine learning is the primary technique after image acquisition
- Mobile apps enable single-step analyses and increase accessibility
- Blink frequency is the main parameter for eyelid movement analysis

Introduction

The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that at least 2.2 billion people have a vision impairment, with at least 1 billion cases preventable or treatable [1]. For example, facial dystonia, a movement disorder characterized by abnormal muscle contractions affecting facial expressions, poses significant challenges to patients' quality of life and social interactions. Also, research indicates that patients with facial dystonia, such as hemifacial spasm (HFS) and blepharospasm (BSP), often experience stigma and discrimination, leading to adverse psychosocial outcomes and decreased quality of life [2].

Benign essential blepharospasm is characterized by progressive involuntary spasms of the eyelid protractors (orbicularis oculi, corrugator, and procerus muscles) that result in eyelid closure [3]. In this context, eyelid blinking and movement analysis are essential for monitoring patients with facial dystonia. Accurately investigating these movements requires methods to capture images of the patient's face and analyze them using specialized software to recognize and quantify eyelid movements [4–7].

The eye diseases such as those above pose a significant global health burden, affecting millions of individuals and causing substantial visual impairment. Recognizing the importance of tools that aid diagnosis and treatment, this study investigates automated methods for evaluating eyelid movement concerning the methodologies, processes, and tools used.

Background and Related Work

Researchers have developed numerous smartphone applications for diagnosis, treatment, and symptom management in ophthalmology. Although systematic evaluation of their purpose, target disease, effectiveness, and utility are essential for effective use, few studies have formally evaluated their validity, reliability, and clinical utility. The report by Nagino and colleagues [8] surveys the state-of-the-art [9], provides an overview of traditional systems'

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analysis alongside modern approaches, and highlights various allied techniques and the impact of transfer learning on ophthalmology for detecting eye diseases. AI and Machine Learning techniques were employed in this research. The findings suggest that AI and allied techniques may transform the medical community, particularly in ophthalmology. Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL)-based approaches, such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), offer the most promising results.

To the best of the author's knowledge, no other reviews or surveys have addressed the automated methods for evaluating eyelid movement, considering the methodologies, processes, and tools used.

Definitions

To maintain clarity in this systematic review, specific terms are defined next.

Eye Aspect Ratio

The Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR) is a quantitative measure to assess eye openness or closure. It is derived by computing the ratio between the distances from the upper and lower eyelids to the corner of the eye.

Ocular Surface Interferometer

The ocular surface interferometer is an imaging device physicians use to assess ocular health in adult patients. It captures images of the tear film, measures lipid layer thickness with nanometer accuracy, and visualizes Meibomian glands using near-infrared illumination. Additionally, it allows examination of the ocular surface and eyelids under white illumination.

Electrooculography (EOG)

Electrooculography (EOG) quantifies the corneo-retinal potential difference between the anterior and posterior regions of the human eye. The resultant signal, the electrooculogram, finds essential applications in ophthalmological diagnostics and eye movement recording.

Methods

This section presents the planning and execution of the systematic literature review (SLR). Writing an SLR comprises the following main activities: planning, conducting, and presenting the results. This methodology was based on Kitchenham's work [10].

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A search was conducted to identify systematic reviews related to the objective of this systematic literature review (SLR). The method used search strings in PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar databases. Table 1 displays the search strings used to identify relevant studies for this SLR and the number of articles retrieved for each search.

However, the search for terms such as ('blepharo' OR 'dystonia' OR 'spasm' OR 'eye disease') AND ('eyelid movement' OR 'blink') AND 'automatic,' applying the filter 'SLR' OR ('systematic' AND 'review') restricted to titles from 2018 onwards, did not yield any systematic literature reviews related to the proposed investigation.

This review explores automatic methods for assessing altered eyelid movements caused by ophthalmological conditions such as blepharospasms, facial dystonias, or dry eye syndrome.

Table 1 - Search string for other SLR

Database	String	Results
PubMed	("blepharo" OR "dystonia" OR "spasm" OR "eye disease") AND ("eyelid movement" OR "blink") AND "automatic" AND ("SLR"[title] OR ("systematic"[Title] AND "review" [Title])) AND 2018/01/01:2024/07/01[dp]	4
Scopus	("blepharo" OR "dystonia" OR "spasm" OR "eye disease") AND ("eyelid movement" OR "blink") AND "automatic" AND DOCTYPE (re) AND LANGUAGE (english) AND PUBYEAR > 2017 AND (TITLE ("slr") OR (TITLE ("systematic") AND TITLE ("review")))	2
Google Scholar	(blepharo dystonia spasm "eye disease") AND ("eyelid movement" blink) AND automatic AND (intitle:slr (intitle:systematic AND intitle:review))	21

Research questions

This systematic literature review investigates the available methods for assessing eyelid movement. To achieve this, the study seeks to address the research questions posed by the authors, as described in Table 2, to guide the research toward its objective.

Table 2 - Research questions

Research questions	Description and motivation
RQ1: What methodologies, processes, or tools are employed for automatically analyzing eyelid movement?	Researchers and practitioners employ a range of methodologies, processes, and tools to automatically analyze eyelid movement. These

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	<p>approaches encompass computer vision techniques, machine learning algorithms, and specialized hardware. By leveraging these resources, investigators can gain insights into blink patterns, eye fatigue, and related phenomena.</p>
RQ2: What parameters are used for analyzing eyelid movement?	<p>Eyelid movement analysis involves assessing specific parameters to understand the dynamics of eyelid function. Researchers investigate factors such as blink rate, duration, amplitude, and velocity. These parameters provide valuable insights into ocular health and potential pathologies. By quantifying eyelid motion, clinicians can diagnose disorders, monitor treatment efficacy, and enhance patient care.</p>
RQ3: What resources are used for capturing and analyzing eyelid movement data?	<p>Eyelid movement data acquisition relies on specialized resources, including high-speed video cameras, infrared sensors, and electrooculography (EOG) systems. These tools enable precise tracking of eyelid motion during blinks, saccades, and other ocular activities.</p>
RQ4: What are the limitations of the methods used for capturing and analyzing eyelid movement data?	<p>This question addresses the main barriers to adopting current eyelid analysis methods, including high costs, need for expert operation, complex setups, and limited accessibility, to guide future improvements in usability and scalability.</p>

Search Strategies

The review protocol employed the PICOC criteria (population, intervention, comparison, outcome, context), as suggested by Kitchenham (Kitchenham & Charters, 2007) [10]. The search string was specified using key terms relevant to the technologies, processes, and tools under investigation. The primary studies were selected from PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar databases. The search itself consists of a web search across these digital databases. Pilot tests were conducted for each database, and the search strings were adapted to account for their specific characteristics. The study's search strings are presented in Table 3.

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Table 3 - Search string

Database	String
PubMed	(blepharo* OR "BSP" OR "Dry eye syndrome" OR "DED" OR "DES" OR "Dry eye disease" OR "Dystonia" OR "Focal dystonia" OR "Eyelid Spasm" OR "Hemifacial Spasm" OR "Keratitis" OR "Lagophthalmos" OR "Ophthalmic Diseases") AND ("Blink rate" OR "eyelid movement" OR "blink dynamics" OR PERCLOS OR "ocular movement" OR "eyelid kinematics") AND ("Algorithm" OR "Automat*" OR "Deep Learning" OR "Machine Learning" OR "SVM" OR "CNN" OR "Neural Network" OR "custom software" OR "objective assessment" OR "high-speed video") AND 2018/01/01:2024/07/01[dp]
Scopus	LANGUAGE (english) AND PUBYEAR > 2017 AND ("blepharoplasty" OR "blepharospasm" OR "bsp" OR "dry eye syndrome" OR "ded" OR "des" OR "dry eye disease" OR "dystonia" OR "focal dystonia" OR "eyelid spasm" OR "hemifacial spasm" OR "hfs" OR "keratitis" OR "lagophthalmos" OR "ophthalmic diseases" OR "eyelid disorder" OR "eyelid disease" OR "eyelid-related disease" OR "computer vision syndrome") AND ("blink rate" OR "eyelid movement" OR "eyelid movements frequency" OR "perclos" OR "eyelid kinematics" OR "eyelid morphological parameter" OR "ocular movement" OR "blinking parameters" OR "blink interval") AND ("algorithm" OR "automation" OR "automatic" OR "deep learning" OR "machine learning" OR "cnn" OR "svm" OR "neural network" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "custom software" OR "custom-made software" OR "high-speed video" OR "objective assessment" OR "high-speed camera" OR "ocular surface interferometer" OR "blocking lenses")
Google Scholar	(Blepharo BSP "Dry eye" "Focal dystonia" "Eyelid Spasm" "Hemifacial Spasm" Keratitis Lagophthalmos "Ophthalmic Disease") AND ("Blink rate" "Eyelid movement" PERCLOS "ocular movement") AND (Algorithm Automat "Deep Learn" "Machine Learn" SVM CNN "Neural Net")

Application of exclusion and inclusion criteria

This study focuses on primary research. The inclusion and exclusion criteria presented in Table 4 were applied to all 905 identified studies. Each article underwent initial analysis based on the title, abstract, and keywords. Additional sections of the article, such as materials and methods, were also examined when necessary.

Table 4 - Exclusion and inclusion criteria

Exclusion and inclusion criteria

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Including criteria	Excluding criteria
I1: Studies that analyze automatic methods for assessing eyelid movement.	E1: Article related to fatigue studies.
	E2: Articles that do not include computational algorithms.
	E3: Studies prior to 2018. Short studies (<= 3 pages).
	E4: Duplicate studies.
	E5: Studies irrelevant to the research, considering the defined research questions.
	E6: Studies not written in English.
	E7: Redundant studies by the same authorship.
	E8: Secondary or tertiary studies (systematic literature reviews, surveys, etc.).
	E9: Publications whose text was not available (through search tools or contacting the authors).

Procedure for studies selection

The studies used in this work were obtained from electronic databases using previously defined search strings. This research identified 905 papers. The removal of duplicate papers reduced the number of works to 844. The application of exclusion criteria further reduced the number of works to 31, which were selected for comprehensive analysis. Table 5 summarizes this process, and Figure 1 illustrates the article selection process.

Table 5 - Summary of the Study Selection Process

Database	Number of papers	Number of papers after excluding duplicates	Number of papers after applying exclusion criteria
PubMed	49	39	3
Scopus	657	646	19
Google Scholar	199	159	9

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Total	905	844	31
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Figure 1 - Summary of the Study Selection Process

Data extraction and synthesis

We created a form to conduct data extraction. Table 6 presents the fields used and the allowed values for these fields.

Table 6 - Data extraction form

Field	Values
Year of publication	
DOI (Digital Object Identifier)	
Authors	
Title	
Originating country of the study	
Article type	Book Chapter Conference Journal Symposium Workshop
Number of patients studied	

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Diseases and/or interventions related to the study	Follow-up of Eyelid Surgeries Facial Dystonias Paralytic Lagophthalmos Dry Eye Syndrome
Parameter used in the study	Average blink duration Blink amplitude Blink frequency Eye aspect ratio (EAR) Maximum Blink Interval (MBI) Maximum velocity of eyelid closure Percentage of closure (PERCLOS)
Model used in the analysis	
Sensor used	
Questionnaires used	Blepharospasm Disability Index (BSDI) Dry Eye Questionnaire (DEQ-5) Hemifacial Spasm Grading System (HSGS) Instant Ocular Symptoms Survey (IOSS) Jankovic Rating Scale (JRS) Japanese version of OSDI (J-OSDI) Numeric Rating Scale (NRS) Ocular Comfort Index (OCI) Ocular Surface Disease Index (OSDI) Symptom Assessment In Dry Eye (SANDE)

Quality assessment

To assess the quality of the selected studies, we created a quality assessment checklist (Table 7). Each question could be evaluated based on the criteria outlined in Table 8, resulting in a numerical value for each study. Consequently, each study could receive a score ranging from 0 (if all answers were "no") to 4 (if all answers were "yes"). Figure 2 presents the distribution of quality scores for the selected studies.

Table 7 - Quality assessment checklist

Question
QC1: Was a method, process, or tool proposed to automatically analyze eyelid movement?
QC2: Were the parameters used to measure eyelid movement clearly defined?
QC3: Was the implemented method validated by an expert?

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QC4: Is the implemented method based on artificial intelligence algorithms?

Table 8 - Quality assessment checklist possible answers

Answer	Weight
Yes	1.0
Partially	0.5
Insufficient information	0.25
No	0.0

Figure 2 - Quality score distribution

Results

By implementing the strategy described in the previous section, relevant studies were selected for this systematic literature review (SLR) based on inclusion and exclusion criteria. Study quality was evaluated using predefined assessment questions, and data were extracted based on the research questions. This section presents the results related to automated methods for assessing eyelid movement.

Studies overview

The studies' publication years range from 2018 to 2024, encompassing the most recent works. Notably, 51% of the studies were published between 2022 and 2023. Figure 3 illustrates these findings.

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Figure 3 - Publication timeline analysis

Brazil, the United States, and China account for 47% of the studies' origins.

When a study is conducted by research institutions in different countries, all countries are associated with the study. Figure 4 illustrates this distribution.

Figure 4 - Country of origin of the study

Journal papers constitute the predominant publication type in the selected studies, accounting for 90%. Figure 5 illustrates the distribution of conference papers and journal papers.

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Figure 5 - Type of paper distribution

This study investigates automatic methods and tools for assessing altered eyelid movement caused by diseases. The researched papers study the following diseases: 55% examine facial dystonias, and 45% examine dry eyes.

The relevance of a study depends on the number of patients studied. Figure 6 illustrates the distribution of studies across patient number ranges, with 61% of the studies involving up to 50 patients and only one study including more than 100 patients.

Figure 6 - Distribution of studies across patient number ranges**RQ1: What methodologies, processes, or tools are employed for automatically analyzing eyelid movement?**

The selected studies employed various methods and tools. Figure 7 illustrates the distribution of studies across the identified methods and tools.

Nine studies employed machine learning techniques, the most common [11–19]. Machine learning algorithms analyze eye images, classifying them and extracting parameters such as EAR (eye aspect ratio), eyelid aperture amplitude, and other dynamic features. These

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parameters provide insights over time, including blink frequency, average blink duration, and maximum inter-blink interval.

Eight studies employed custom software [5–7,20–24]. These custom solutions are purpose-built for specific tasks. However, the studies do not delve into the construction details and instead focus on presenting the resulting data from their utilization.

Four studies have employed mobile applications [4,25–27]. Notably, their emergence in 2022 indicates a recent trend. These mobile apps allow for analysis in a single step and are accessible to a broader audience due to the widespread use of smartphones.

Two studies featured ocular surface interferometers [28,29]. These devices can extract metrics related to blink profiles, including blink frequency and duration.

Electrooculography (EOG) has been employed in two studies [30,31]. This method enables the monitoring of eyelid movement using electrodes positioned around the eyes.

A study [32] employed a smart glasses device utilizing skin pressure sensors. Wearable devices offer the advantage of enabling continuous patient monitoring over an extended duration.

A study by [33] employed radio frequency signal analysis. This technique enables the convenient extraction of the blink biomarker without direct patient contact.

In a study by [34], magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) analysis was employed with electromyography.

The eye-tracker device was used in a study by [35] to extract blink frequency and interval.

Electromyography was utilized in a study by [36] for blink frequency extraction.

A study by [37] employed a wearable device with an electromagnetic sensor to extract blink frequency.

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Figure 7 - Methods employed in the selected studies to analyze eyelid movements**RQ2: What parameters are used for analyzing eyelid movement?**

This research question aimed to determine the parameters most used to analyze eyelid movement. Several parameters were employed to assess eyelid motion. The most prevalent parameter was blink frequency, which appeared in 77% of the selected studies. Two different parameters were utilized in 11 studies, and three were employed in 2 studies to evaluate eyelid movement. Figure 8 presents the distribution of parameters used in the selected studies.

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Figure 8 - Parameter used in study distribution**RQ3: What resources are used for capturing and analyzing eyelid movement data?**

Figure 9 illustrates the distribution of the sensors employed. The preferred method for capturing eyelid movement data involves using cameras. This category includes mobile device cameras, standard cameras, webcams, and commercial ophthalmic devices. Additionally, in two studies, wearable devices utilizing eye-tracking technology rely on cameras to track eyelid movement [34,35].

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Figure 9 - Sensors

RQ4: What are the limitations of the methods used for capturing and analyzing eyelid movement data?

Various methods exist for analyzing eyelid movement, each with distinct limitations. Using commercial ophthalmic equipment requires the expertise of an ophthalmic professional, and the associated costs can pose a limitation.

Custom software methods require specialized software, which can be costly to develop. In certain instances, manual work is necessary to prepare input data and interpret output data. Often, an information technology specialist must conduct the analysis.

Image acquisition methods relying on camera-captured images may necessitate a specialized illumination setup to ensure high-quality image capture.

The high costs of wearable devices make them less affordable for many consumers. Additionally, safety concerns related to wearable devices, such as data security vulnerabilities, act as limitations.

Electromyography (EMG) and electrooculography (EOG) require specialized personnel for both analysis setup and interpretation of output data.

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Custom hardware solutions remain experimental, and their limited availability significantly constrains the widespread adoption of these methods.

Conclusion

This paper presents a systematic literature review that investigates studies analyzing automated methods for assessing altered eyelid movements. The review reveals that image analysis is the dominant approach for extracting eyelid-related parameters, appearing in 20 of the 31 selected studies. Following image acquisition, machine learning emerges as the primary technique for parameter extraction. Recent advancements in mobile applications have simplified the study of eyelid movements, allowing for streamlined analyses and increased accessibility. Among the various parameters analyzed, blink frequency is the most utilized parameter for eyelid movement analysis, with cameras serving as the primary sensor for capturing eyelid movements.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Gustavo Adolpho Bonesso: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Carlos Marcelo Gurjão de Godoy:** Writing – review & editing. **Regina Célia Coelho:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Validation, Project administration, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Funding sources

This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Acknowledgments

This study is part of a master's degree dissertation supported by the Biomedical Computing Laboratory at the Science and Technology Institute, Federal University of São Paulo.

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APPENDIX B

A Mobile Application Approach to Help Analyzing Eyelid Movements from Videos

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Abstract. Monitoring eyelid blinking and movement is crucial for patients with facial dystonia. This work presents a novel mobile application approach to assess eyelid movement of eye-opening and closing over time obtained from patients' videos. The application analyzes the frequency and amplitude of altered eye movements in patients with blepharospasm who received Botox treatment. The application used the Flutter platform, offering cross-platform compatibility for Android and iOS devices, ensuring widespread accessibility. The chosen architectural framework, clean architecture, enhances maintainability, reduces complexity, and improves codebase modifications, contributing to robust, easily upgradable applications. Hive, a NoSQL database solution for Flutter applications, managed local databases. Its integration offers robust storage and retrieval, aiding data analysis. As for the machine learning used, the eyelid opening states were analyzed using the Google ML Kit's Face Detection API, which is optimized for mobile devices and capable of discerning specific facial contours. The application collected data from videos of subjects with blepharospasm before and after Botox treatment, calculating eye-opening probabilities to track clinical progression accurately. Results demonstrated significant improvements in eye-opening probability post-treatment, confirming its effectiveness in capturing changes in eyelid movement. Further analysis using graphical representation and data export to Excel facilitated detailed comparisons and enhanced clinical understanding. The application's usability extends beyond clinical settings, enabling patients to monitor their progress at home. This accessibility, coupled with its effectiveness in assessing eyelid movement disorders and treatment outcomes, underscores the utility of mobile technology in healthcare, benefiting both professionals and patients. Overall, this study showcases the potential of mobile applications in tracking and evaluating complex physiological parameters, offering a convenient and effective tool for advancing medical diagnostics and patient care, especially to aid public health services, such as The Brazilian Unified Health System (SUS).

Keywords: Eyelid movement assessment · Mobile Application · Machine learning

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1 Introduction

Eye diseases pose a significant global health burden, affecting millions of individuals and causing substantial visual impairment. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that at least 2.2 billion people have a vision impairment, with at least 1 billion cases preventable or treatable [5].

Facial dystonia, a movement disorder characterized by abnormal muscle contractions affecting facial expressions, poses significant challenges to patients' quality of life and social interactions. Research indicates that patients with facial dystonia, such as hemifacial spasm (HFS) and blepharospasm (BSP), often experience stigma and discrimination, leading to adverse psychosocial outcomes and decreased quality of life [6].

Benign essential blepharospasm (BEB) is a disorder characterized by progressive involuntary spasms of the eyelid protractors (orbicularis oculi, corrugator, and procerus muscles) that result in eyelid closure [7].

Analysis of eyelid blinking and movement is essential for monitoring patients with facial dystonia. The objective investigation of these movements requires methods to capture images of the patient's face and submit these images to specialized software analysis to recognize and quantify eyelid movements [1–4].

Image capture can be performed using external cameras [2, 3] or even the cameras present in mobile devices [1, 4]. Specialized software, like MATLAB, can perform subsequent analysis to detect eyelid movement [2]. The eyelid movement analysis can also be done using web pages accessed by mobile devices or desktops [1].

The present work presents a mobile application capable of assessing eyelid movement by recording the opening and closing of the eyes over time obtained from patients' videos. This tool facilitates the analysis of the frequency and amplitude of regular and altered movements.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Software Framework

The application development occurred by using the Flutter platform, which is cross-platform. It allows for the generation of Android and iOS mobile operating systems applications, covering virtually the entire smartphone user base [8].

The selected architectural framework for guiding app development is clean architecture, which yields advantages such as improved maintainability, reduced complexity, streamlined codebase modifications, and the creation of robust, easily upgradable, and verifiable applications, ultimately enhancing software quality and adaptability to evolving requirements and technological advancements [10, 11].

The selected tool for local database manipulation is Hive, a NoSQL database manipulation solution tailored for Flutter applications' local storage requirements [9]. Hive offers integration with Flutter, furnishing a robust API for data storage and retrieval. This feature set renders it suitable for managing modest to moderate datasets within applications.

The Hive tool utilizes the JSON format for unstructured data storage. Within this framework, entities serve as representations of specific system concepts. The AnalysisEntity, a central component, stores analysis data and includes essential attributes. These attributes encompass analysisDateTime (which captures the date and time of analysis), duration (pertaining to video duration), and an array named frameList. The frameList contains frame-specific details, represented by the FrameEntity. As a sub-entity of the AnalysisEntity, the FrameEntity possesses attributes such as frameNumber, frameDateTime, and probabilities of eye-opening for each eye—stored respectively as rightEyeOpenness and leftEyeOpenness. An example with data from the AnalysisEntity and FrameEntity is shown in Fig. 1.

```

AnalysisEntity
{
  "analysisDateTime": "2024-04-23T11:21:30.0",
  "duration": 5.0,
  "frameList": [
    {
      "frameNumber": 0,
      "frameDateTime": "2024-04-23T11:21:30.0",
      "rightEyeOpenness": 0.9956856369972229,
      "leftEyeOpenness": 0.998312771320343
    },
    ...
    {
      "frameNumber": 124,
      "frameDateTime": "2024-04-23T11:21:34.96",
      "rightEyeOpenness": 0.898965235782322,
      "leftEyeOpenness": 0.80787288723898928
    }
  ]
}

```

Fig. 1. Example with data from the AnalysisEntity and FrameEntity

As for the machine learning used in the present work, it was used a Computer Vision Application Programming Interface (API) to analyze the eyelid opening states using the Google ML Kit [12]. Optimized for mobile devices, ML Kit conducts all processing locally on the device. Specifically, the Google ML Kit module designated for this task is Face Detection, facilitating the detection of eye contours and other facial features to recognize the state of eyelid opening.

The Google ML Kit receives an image as input and conducts face detection. The framework is capable of detecting multiple faces within a single image. However, the application only considered the first detected face, assuming the app will analyze the user individually. After face detection, the framework proceeds to classify the status of the eyes. This classification provides a probability value indicating the degree of openness for each eye.

The Google ML Kit demonstrates the capacity to discern specific facial contours, including those corresponding to the eyes, nose, and mouth. When face contour detection activates, a corresponding list of points is provided for each detected facial feature,

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delineating the shape of the respective feature. Figure 2 illustrates the mapping of these points onto a facial structure.

Fig. 2. Face contour detection by Google ML Kit (https://developers.google.com/static/ml-kit/vision/face-detection/images/face_contours.svg)

The criterion employed to determine a blink is the probability of eye-opening falling below 50% in a frame.

2.2 Data Sources

The data was collected in 2-min videos from subjects who agreed to participate in the study. The device used to record the videos is an iPhone 6s, Apple. The recorded videos have a resolution of 1920×108 pixels at 120 frames per second (FPS). The application evaluated videos from five patients with blepharospasm who underwent Botox treatment. The average eye-opening probability was calculated for each patient before and after the treatment. The subjects from the Division of Ophthalmic Plastic Surgery, Department of Ophthalmology and Visual Sciences, Federal University of São Paulo, were recruited to participate.

2.3 Pre-recorded Video Processing

Pre-recorded video analysis occurred in stages, as depicted in Fig. 3. In the first stage, the video is divided into frames. Each frame is stored in a temporary directory for subsequent processing.

Fig. 3. Pre-recorded video processing sequence

Each stored frame is loaded in the second stage to analyze the eye-opening state. Google ML Kit attempts to detect a face in the image. Upon detecting a face, facial feature data is extracted. If the algorithm does not detect a face, it skips that frame and attempts to detect a face in the next frame. For our study, the relevant information is each eye's probability of eye-opening. Frame number and timestamp information are also stored in a JSON format frame vector.

As for the final stage, the data stored in this vector is written to a local database and made available for further analysis. The application can export this data in Excel format to facilitate analysis using other tools.

3 Compliance with Ethical Requirements

The Federal University of São Paulo Review Board approved this study (CAAE89528618.4.0000.5505), and all patients were treated according to the Declaration of Helsinki.

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4 Results and Discussion

Figure 4 depicts the application's initial screen developed to analyze eyelid movement. The application processed videos of the studied patients, generating the data presented in this study.

Fig. 4. Initial screen of the app

Figure 5 illustrates the application interface for pre-recorded video processing.

Google ML Kit detects the eyes and generates 16 coordinates for each eye, which, in turn, allows drawing an approximate contour of the eye shape. Figure 6 shows the application screen that shows the highlighted eye region and the eye contours. Figure 6 also depicts the probability graph of eyes being open over time, as the vertical axis ranges from 0 (0%) to 1 (100%), and horizontal axis refers to the frame number. The vertical black bar in the graph's center corresponds to the image's highlighted frame.

Fig. 5. Application interface for pre-recorded video processing

Fig. 6. Eye detection. Highlighted eye region and the eye contours (upper panel). The probability graph (bottom panel) represents the eyes that are open over time. Vertical axis range: 0 (0%) to 1 (100%). Horizontal axis: frame number. The black vertical bar refers to the image on the upper panel.

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Table 1 shows the average eye-opening probability obtained by the evaluation of videos from five patients with blepharospasm who underwent Botox treatment. For all cases, the application successfully captured improvement, demonstrating that patients, on average, spend more time with their eyes open after the Botox treatment, as clinically expected [2].

Table 1. Eye openness before and after treatment

	Eye openness average before treatment	Eye openness average after treatment
Patient 1	0,59	0,97
Patient 2	0,64	0,88
Patient 3	0,56	0,93
Patient 4	0,80	0,90
Patient 5	0,47	0,81

The data exported to Excel enables a more detailed analysis. Figure 7(a) illustrates the eye-opening probability graphs for both eyes, filtered for the first 60 s before treatment of a given patient. Figure 7(b) displays the same information for the patient after treatment.

The clinical tests with the applicative demonstrated the clinical progression of patients with blepharospasm, indicating the change in the duration during which the eyes remain open before and after treatment. Additionally, patients can use it to monitor their progress at home, as the application is available for download and can be used on any smartphone.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 7. Patient 2 analysis data (a) before treatment and (b) after treatment

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, this study successfully developed a mobile application capable of assessing eyelid movement by recording eye-opening and closing over time. The application effectively analyzed the frequency and amplitude of eyelid movements, particularly in patients with blepharospasm who underwent Botox treatment.

The results from videos of five patients showed a significant improvement in eye-opening probability post-treatment, indicating the application's ability to capture changes in eyelid movement. Further analysis using Excel data export and graphical representation demonstrated the clinical progression of patients, allowing for a detailed comparison of eye-opening duration before and after treatment. Moreover, the applicative's usability extends to patients' self-monitoring at home, as it is accessible for smartphone download. Overall, this study highlights the utility of mobile technology in tracking and evaluating eyelid movement disorders and treatment outcomes, offering a non-invasive

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convenient tool for healthcare professionals and patients, potentially aiding public health services, such as The Brazilian Unified Health System (SUS), or Sistema Único de Saúde in Portuguese (https://www.gov.br/saude/en?set_language=en - accessed on May 10th, 2024).

The future steps of the present work involve enhancing real-time data processing as it would help, for example, implementing live monitoring features, exploring wearable device integration, using machine learning for better recognition, developing remote patient management, and gathering user feedback for improvements.

Conflict of Interest. All the authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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APPENDIX C

TECNOLOGIA DE INTELIGÊNCIA ARTIFICIAL NA AVALIAÇÃO DO PISCAR EM TEMPO REAL

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OBJETIVO

O piscar pode ser afetado por diversas condições, como olho seco, blefaroespasm, espasmo hemifacial e lagofalmo. A avaliação objetiva do piscar requer métodos para capturar imagens da face do paciente, juntamente com softwares especializados para reconhecer e analisar os movimentos das pálpebras e o estado de abertura dos olhos. A captura de imagens pode ser feita por câmeras convencionais ou por câmeras acopladas a smartphones. A maioria dos estudos sobre o piscar baseia-se na contagem manual dos movimentos das pálpebras ou em sistemas complexos compostos por duas etapas, que envolvem o uso de câmeras externas para a captura de imagens e softwares em desktops para análise posterior. Esses métodos costumam ser impraticáveis para uso clínico.

Nós desenvolvemos um aplicativo para smartphone que usa a câmera do celular para a captura do piscar e um software customizado desenvolvido para detectar os olhos, determinar o seu grau de abertura e gerar uma análise sobre o piscar em tempo real no próprio dispositivo móvel. O software foi desenvolvido utilizando a plataforma Flutter, incorporando ferramentas de inteligência artificial (machine learning). Este estudo visa apresentar o aplicativo BLINK para dispositivos móveis, desenvolvido utilizando tecnologia de inteligência artificial para análise do piscar em tempo real.

MATERIAL E MÉTODOS

O piscar espontâneo foi registrado bilateralmente usando o aplicativo em um iPhone 13 (Apple Inc., Cupertino, CA). Todas as gravações foram realizadas com os participantes na posição primária do olhar, sob condições padronizadas. Participantes com condições que afetassem as pálpebras, a superfície ocular ou a função neurológica, e que pudessem influenciar o piscar, foram excluídos.

O aplicativo utiliza um modelo de aprendizado de máquina (machine learning) para estimar a probabilidade de abertura dos olhos. Para aprimorar a acurácia na detecção de piscadas, foi implementado um algoritmo que utiliza três limiares distintos (Fig.1): um limiar superior para indicar o início da piscada, um limiar inferior para caracterizar piscadas completas, e um limiar de retorno que determina o fim da piscada. A detecção tem início quando a probabilidade de abertura dos olhos cai abaixo de 0,75; caso esse valor atinja níveis inferiores a 0,25, a piscada é classificada como completa. O piscar é considerado finalizado quando a probabilidade retorna a valores superiores a 0,98. Esse conjunto de limiares minimiza falsos positivos decorrentes de pequenas flutuações e permite distinguir com maior precisão entre piscadas parciais e completas.

O aplicativo permite configurar o tempo de duração, a resolução do vídeo e gravar o vídeo que será analisado em tempo real, quadro a quadro (Fig.2). Imediatamente após a gravação do vídeo usando-se o aplicativo, é gerada uma tela com o traçado e a análise do piscar (Fig. 3).

Para avaliar a eficácia do aplicativo na detecção do piscar, as contagens de piscadas geradas automaticamente pelo app foram comparadas com contagens realizadas manualmente a partir dos vídeos gravados pelo próprio aplicativo. A análise utilizou o erro quadrático médio (root mean square error - RMSE), uma medida frequentemente utilizada para avaliar erros de predição em modelos de aprendizado de máquinas. Os valores de RMSE variam de 0,0 a 1,0, com valores mais próximos de zero indicando maior precisão preditiva do modelo.

Fig.1 Algoritmo usado para para estimar a probabilidade de abertura dos olhos

Fig. 2 Sequência de quadros (frames) e gráfico correspondente detectado pelo aplicativo mostrando como o app detecta cada estado de abertura ocular, quadro a quadro

Fig. 3 Exemplo de análise do piscar fornecida em tempo real pelo app

RESULTADOS

O aplicativo registrou os vídeos utilizando a câmera do celular e os analisou em tempo real. Foram avaliados vídeos de 34 participantes; 3 vídeos foram excluídos devido à qualidade da imagem. A média de idade dos participantes deste estudo foi de $36,85 \pm 13,11$ anos.

O aplicativo registrou uma média de $20,66 \pm 12,06$ piscadas por minuto (ppm), em comparação com uma média de $20,78 \pm 12,31$ ppm obtida a partir das contagens manuais. A precisão do aplicativo, medida pelo RMSE, foi de 0,088, indicando um alto nível de precisão na detecção do piscar.

CONCLUSÃO

O aplicativo BLINK, uma ferramenta prática que usa tecnologia de inteligência artificial para análise do piscar em tempo real em smartphones, demonstrou desempenho confiável na detecção do piscar. Uma versão aprimorada deste sistema poderia facilitar avaliações de piscar em diversas condições, permitindo que pacientes monitorem distúrbios como olho seco, blefaroespasm, espasmo hemifacial e paralisia facial. O aplicativo também poderá ser utilizado na prática clínica para avaliar objetivamente como cirurgias palpebrais afetam o piscar. O sistema apresenta ainda potencial para integração com plataformas de telemedicina e uso em pesquisas clínicas.

Estamos trabalhando na incorporação de parâmetros adicionais de análise, como amplitude, duração e velocidade do piscar, a fim de ampliar ainda mais o potencial uso do aplicativo na prática clínica e promover sua disponibilização para a comunidade médica.

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APPENDIX D

Mobile-Based Automated Eyelid Blink Detection and Movement Analysis: A Machine Learning Approach

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Abstract. Eye diseases pose a significant global health challenge, affecting millions of people and leading to substantial visual impairment. Analyzing eyelid blinking and movement is crucial for monitoring patients with abnormal eyelid motions. This paper introduces the so-called Bapp (Blink Application), a mobile application designed to evaluate eyelid movement by recording the opening and closing of the eyes over time and detecting eye blinks using a machine-learning approach. The application processes pre-recorded videos and then validates the results against publicly available datasets. The proposed system operates in a unified stage, utilizing the pre-recorded video as input and evaluating the degree of eyelid openness in each frame using predictions from Google ML Kit, a machine learning-based framework integrated into the Flutter platform. The results are stored in a local database and can be exported to Excel for further analysis. Developed on the Flutter platform, the Bapp supports multiple languages, ensuring accessibility to a broad audience. The blink prediction results align with those obtained from other methods applied to the same dataset, demonstrating the app's effectiveness in objectively monitoring the clinical progression of patients with eyelid diseases.

Keywords: Eyelid Movement · Blink Detection · Mobile Health Application

1 Introduction

Eye diseases are a primary global health concern, impacting millions of people and leading to significant visual impairment. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), at least 2.2 billion people experience vision impairment, with at least 1 billion cases being preventable or treatable.¹

¹ World Health Organization (2023) Blindness and vision impairment, <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/blindness-and-visual-impairment>.

It is essential to analyze eyelid blinking and movement to monitor patients with abnormal eyelid movements. Objectively assessing these movements involves capturing images of the patient's face and processing them using specialized software to recognize and quantify eyelid movements [1–4]. Unfortunately, such approaches often involve complex systems impractical for clinical settings. Besides, they are frequently imprecise, especially for patients with abnormal eyelid movements, and fail to capture other critical parameters, such as amplitude movements [1–4].

Image capture can occur by using external cameras [2, 3] or the built-in cameras of mobile devices [1, 4]. Subsequent analysis can occur using computational tools such as MATLAB to detect and measure eyelid movement [2]. Alternatively, web-based platforms accessed via mobile devices or desktops can also facilitate such studies [5].

This work introduces a mobile application designed to evaluate eyelid movement by recording the opening and closing of the eyes over time. The application leverages a machine learning approach, focusing on the pre-recorded video feature, which validates the app's results against a public dataset [6].² The tool provides a robust framework for analyzing the frequency and amplitude of normal and pathological eyelid movements, offering a scalable and accessible solution for clinical and research applications.

2 Related Works

Advancements in technology have significantly enhanced the analysis of eyelid blinking and movement, particularly for patient monitoring in clinical settings. Techniques such as high-speed imaging, deep learning, and smartphone videography have emerged, providing precise and non-invasive methods to assess blink dynamics and their implications for various ocular conditions.

High-speed imaging combined with digital image correlation (DIC) allows for detailed measurement of eyelid motion during blinking. This method captures kinematic data, including blink duration, eyelid displacements, and peak velocities, facilitating a comprehensive analysis of spontaneous and reflex blinks [7].

Intelligent vision measurement systems utilizing deep learning can analyze blinking characteristics, offering insights into the visual function of patients, particularly those with dry eye disease. These systems automatically calculate blink completeness and provide stable, accurate measurements, enhancing clinical assessments [8, 9].

Smartphone videography has proven effective in capturing eyelid movements, allowing for comparative analysis of blink dynamics in patients with conditions like chronic progressive external ophthalmoplegia and facial nerve palsy. This method is cost-effective and accessible, making it suitable for both clinical and research applications [10].

There are limited integrated mobile apps for objectively analyzing eyelid movements in the present work approach. The DryEyeRhythm app, which diagnoses dry eye disease, was developed in Japan through a consignment agreement with Juntendo University Graduate School of Medicine and InnoJin Inc., Tokyo [11].

² Talking Face Video, https://personalpages.manchester.ac.uk/staff/timothy.f.cootes/data/talking_face/talking_face.html.

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The EyeScore mobile application, developed by the Department of Clinical Research at the Westview Eye Institute in San Diego, CA, USA, utilizes blink rates and patterns as early clinical biomarkers for dry eye disease. Although designed for iOS, it is still unavailable for download [12].

Another approach involves hosting the application on a cloud server. The videos are recorded locally with a camera or smartphone and sent to a web server that processes them and reports the eyelid movement results. One project that utilized this technology employed Streamlit to host the application [1].

While all these technological advancements offer significant benefits in monitoring eyelid movement, challenges remain in standardizing these methods across diverse clinical settings and ensuring their widespread adoption. Further research is needed to validate these technologies' effectiveness and reliability in various patient populations.

3 Proposed Method

For clarity, Fig. 1 illustrates the steps and tools used in the proposed method. To validate the mobile application Bapp (Blink Application), we used videos from two reference datasets as input (Eyeblink8 and Talking Face), which have annotations indicating where the blinks occur. These videos were processed by Bapp using the feature for pre-recorded video analysis. This feature analyzes each frame from the video to assess the openness of each eye using Google ML Kit (a machine learning tool) and stores the results in Hive (a local database). The next step in validation is to export the raw analysis results from Bapp to Excel, enabling comparison with the annotations from the reference datasets to check Bapp's efficiency in detecting blinks in the input videos. Bapp addresses the limitations associated with the clinical application of eyelid movement monitoring by providing an automated, precise, and clinically feasible solution. The system performs eyelid movement analysis in a unified, integrated stage.

Fig. 1. Diagram with steps and tools used to analyze eyelid movements from dataset reference videos and compare the results from the Bapp mobile application to the annotated data from the datasets

3.1 Eyeblink Detection Dataset

This work used Eyeblink8 [6] and Talking Face³, two public eyeblink detection datasets. The Eyeblink8 dataset contains over 82,600 frames and 408 blinks. It includes natural facial movements, expressions, and other intensive non-blink motions. The Talking Face dataset comprises 5,000 frames, corresponding to approximately 200 s of recording, capturing a subject engaged in a natural conversation with another person. The video recording uses a static camera to model facial behavior during the interaction. The dataset includes 61 additional blinks, raising the total blinks annotated to 469.

The annotations for each video are provided in two files: the first lists the frame numbers and their acquisition times, while the second contains manually annotated eye states.

Each row in the annotation file contains the following information: Frame ID, Blink ID, NF, LE_FC, LE_NV, RE_FC, RE_NV.

- Frame ID: Frame counter
- Blink ID: A unique blink ID; the eye blink interval definition occurs as a sequence of frames with the same blink ID.
- No frontal face (NF): An eye blink occurs when the subject looks sideways, given that the variable changes from X to N.
- Left eye (LE), right eye (RE), face (F)
- Eye fully closed (FC): If the subject's eyes are closed from 90% to 100%, the flag changes from X to C.
- Eye not visible (NV): While the subject's eye is not visible because of the hand, bad light conditions, hair, or even too fast head movement, this variable changes from X to N.

3.2 Software Tools

The Bapp mobile application was developed using the Flutter development tool.⁴ It enables the creation of cross-platform mobile applications for Android and iOS operating systems using the same codebase, thus covering nearly the entire smartphone user base. The application supports three languages—Portuguese, English, and Spanish—by utilizing Flutter's localization library, which ensures a broad and diverse audience.

Clean architecture is the chosen architectural framework for guiding the development of Bapp mobile applications. It offers advantages such as improved maintainability, reduced complexity, streamlined codebase modifications, and the development of robust, easily upgradable, and verifiable applications. Those features enhance software quality and adaptability to evolving requirements and technological advancements [13].⁵

Concerning the analysis of the eyelid opening states, the framework relies on using Google ML Kit, an application programming interface (API) for computer vision developed by Google.⁶ We used a plugin to integrate Google ML Kit into the Flutter platform.

³ Talking Face Video, https://personalpages.manchester.ac.uk/staff/timothy.f.cootes/data/talking_face/talking_face.html.

⁴ Flutter Flutter Developer Tools, <https://flutter.dev>.

⁵ Martin R (2012) The Clean Architecture, <https://blog.cleancoder.com/uncle-bob/2012/08/13/the-clean-architecture.html>.

⁶ Google ML Kit | Google for Developers, <https://developers.google.com/ml-kit/guides>.

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Optimized for mobile devices, the Google ML Kit performs all processing locally on the device. The specific Google ML Kit module used in this task is Face Detection. It enabled the detection of eye openness probability, eye contours, and other facial features to recognize the state of eyelid opening.

The Google ML Kit receives an image as input and performs face detection. Even though the framework can identify multiple faces within a single image, the Bapp mobile application considers only the first detected face, as the app analyzes the user individually. After detecting a face, the framework proceeds to classify the status of the eyes. This classification provides a probability value indicating the degree of openness for each eye.

The selected local database is Hive, a NoSQL solution tailored to the local storage needs of Flutter applications.⁷ Hive integrates seamlessly with Flutter and offers a robust data storage and retrieval API. The Hive database allows information to be stored using JSON format.

3.3 Eye Blink Detection Algorithm

The interpretation of raw data from Google ML Kit detects the frames where a blink occurred. The first approach to detecting eye blinks involved determining a blink when the probability of eye openness drops below 0.5, where “0.0” represents “totally closed eye” and “1.0” refers to “totally opened eye”. Figure 2 illustrates a problem with this method: When the probability bounces around probability 0.5 - falling below 0.5, rising above 0.5, and then falling again below 0.5 - the algorithm counts two blinks, which is incorrect, as only one blink or no blink would have happened.

Fig. 2. Illustration of the problem of eye openness probability chart with two frames below probability 0.5.

Using a single threshold to indicate a blink is not a practical solution. To solve this problem, considering two distinct thresholds - one to signal the start of the blink and another to mark its end - achieves better outcomes. Implementing a third threshold further differentiates between partial and complete blinks. Figure 3 illustrates these thresholds.

⁷ Isar Database Hive, <https://github.com/isar/hive>.

Fig. 3. Illustration of probability charts with thresholds indicating the beginning and ending of partial or complete blinks.

The pseudocode for eye blink detection is in Fig. 4.

```

BEGIN

    DEFINE partial_blink_detected AS FALSE
    DEFINE full_blink_detected AS FALSE

    IF eye_open_probability < 0.75 THEN
        IDENTIFY partial_blink
        SET partial_blink_detected TO TRUE
    END IF

    IF eye_open_probability < 0.25 THEN
        IDENTIFY full_blink
        SET full_blink_detected TO TRUE
    END IF

    IF eye_open_probability > 0.98 AND
        (partial_blink_detected OR full_blink_detected) THEN
        END blink
        SET partial_blink_detected TO FALSE
        SET full_blink_detected TO FALSE
    END IF

END

```

Fig. 4. Pseudocode for blink detection algorithm

Figure 5(a) illustrates an instance of a partial blink, where the eye openness probability decreases below 0.75 but remains above the 0.25 threshold, which characterizes a complete blink. The blink is classified as complete upon the eye openness probability returning to 0.98. Figure 5(b) demonstrates a complete blink when the eye openness probability drops below 0.25.

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(a)

(b)

Fig. 5. Illustration of probability charts of partial blink (a) and complete blink (b)

3.4 Pre-recorded Video Processing

The first step involves dividing the video into frames for individual analysis. For each frame, the Google ML Kit detects faces. When face detection occurs, it calculates the likelihood of the eyes being open, which ranges from 0 (closed) to 1 (open). The local database registers the data for later analysis of the start and end of the blinks. Figure 6 illustrates the sequence of processing the pre-recorded video.

Fig. 6. Pre-recorded video processing sequence

For each analysis, the Bapp stores date and time information, duration, and an array of details from each frame within an AnalysisEntity. Consequently, the FrameEntity operates as a sub-entity of the AnalysisEntity, with every frame documenting the frame number, date, time, and the detected probability of eye-opening. Figure 7 shows an example with data from the AnalysisEntity and FrameEntity.

```

{
  "analysisDateTime": "2024-04-23T11:21:30.0",
  "duration": 5.0,
  "frameList": [
    {
      "frameNumber": 0,
      "frameDateTime": "2024-04-23T11:21:30.0",
      "rightEyeOpenness": 0.9956856369972229,
      "leftEyeOpenness": 0.998312771320343
    },
    ...
    {
      "frameNumber": 124,
      "frameDateTime": "2024-04-23T11:21:34.96",
      "rightEyeOpenness": 0.898965235782322,
      "leftEyeOpenness": 0.80787288723898928
    }
  ]
}

```

Fig. 7. Analysis example with data from the AnalysisEntity and FrameEntity

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3.5 Excel Export

The export to Excel feature saves an analysis's raw data in an Excel sheet. This functionality is valuable for debugging and provides flexibility in viewing data. It also allows sorting, filtering, and performing operations on the raw data to understand the analysis's results better.

The Excel export feature is crucial for comparing the dataset's video analysis results with the annotated blink information to calculate metrics such as RMSE and precision.

As shown in Fig. 8, this feature is accessed via the Export to Excel button on the Analysis Detail screen.

Fig. 8. A screenshot of the Bapp mobile application illustrating the analysis detail screen, with the "Export to Excel" button at the bottom.

Figure 9 shows the exported Excel sheet containing information about each frame's overall analysis and eye status. This information allows the user to work more flexibly with the raw data and possibly gain more insights.

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	A	B	C	D	E	
1	Patient	Gustavo Bonesso				
2	Analysis type	AnalysisType.realTime				
3	*** Pre/Post Inter	PrePostIntervention.pre				
4	*** Days Pre/Pos	15				
5	*** Observations					
6	Duration	4.4 seconds				
7	Number of Blinks L:	4	R: 4			
8	Blink Frequency: L:	54.1 BPM	R: 54.1 BPM			
9	FPS:	16.0 FPS				
10						
11	***Frame	***Right Eye Ope	***Left Eye Oper	***Right Eye EAI	***Left Eye EAR	
12		0	0,99	0,95	0,25	0,26
13		1	0,99	0,95	0,26	0,28
14		2	0,99	0,95	0,25	0,28
15		3	0,99	0,99	0,28	0,28
16		4	0,99	0,95	0,28	0,29
17		5	0,99	0,95	0,26	0,28

Fig. 9. Excel sheet displaying raw data from the analysis

3.6 Validation

The app processes videos from the EyeBlink8 and Talking Face public datasets to validate its efficiency in detecting blinks. The eye blink is considered detected if there is any intersection between the detected blink and the annotation. The intersection interval with the ground truth is counted just one as a True Positive. The results are exported to Excel spreadsheets and compared using the root mean square error (RMSE). The results were normalized using the StandardScaler function and evaluated using the evaluation metric 'mean_squared_error', both from Scikit-Learn.⁸

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=0}^n (y - \hat{y})^2} \quad (1)$$

where \hat{y} is a vector with the predicted values, and y is the ground truth value for each value analyzed. The result is the root of the difference between the predicted and the ground truth values divided by the number of values (value represented by n).

To compare the results to other papers using the same datasets, we used the following equations:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (2)$$

$$Recall(TPrate) = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (3)$$

$$FPrate = \frac{FP}{N} \quad (4)$$

⁸ scikit-learn - Machine Learning in Python, <https://scikit-learn.org/>

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$$MA = \frac{TP + TN}{P + N} \quad (5)$$

where TP is True Positive (the eye blinks are annotated in the reference dataset and were predicted by the app), FP is False Positive (when the app predicts the eye blink, but it is not found in the annotated dataset), FN is False Negative (when an eye blink is annotated in the dataset but not predicted by the app). N is the number of frames with open eyes. MA is the mean accuracy. TN is the True Negative, calculated by subtracting the TP, FP, and FN frames from the total number of frames of the videos. P is calculated by subtracting the total number of frames from N.

4 Results

The analysis starts after selecting a video from the smartphone's gallery. Figure 10 shows the Bapp mobile application interface for processing pre-recorded videos.

Fig. 10. Screenshot of the Bapp mobile application interface for processing pre-recorded videos.

After completing the analysis, Bapp displays the analysis detail screen shown in Fig. 11. This screen presents the analysis data, including the analysis date, duration, number of blinks detected, calculated blink frequency per minute, and a graphical representation for enhanced visual clarity.

Fig. 11. Screenshot of the Bapp mobile application displaying the detailed analysis information.

Fig. 12. Frames sequence for the first blink in the Talking Face video

Figure 12 shows a frame sequence from one of the videos used to validate the first blink annotated in the dataset.

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Table 1 shows the annotated reference for the first blink from the Talking Face video. It determines the beginning of the blink in the frame 168 and the end of the blink in the frame 176.

Table 1. Annotated frames for the first blink in the Talking Face video

Frame_ID	Blink_ID	NFF	LE_FC	LE_NV	RE_FC	RE_NV
166	-1	X	X	X	X	X
167	-1	X	X	X	X	X
168	1	X	X	X	X	X
169	1	X	X	X	X	X
170	1	X	C	X	C	X
171	1	X	C	X	C	X
172	1	X	X	X	X	X
173	1	X	X	X	X	X
174	1	X	X	X	X	X
175	1	X	X	X	X	X
176	1	X	X	X	X	X
177	-1	X	X	X	X	X

Figure 13 shows the chart of openness probability for both eyes predicted by Google ML Kit for the first blink in the Talking Face video.

Fig. 13. Eye openness probability for both eyes predicted by Google ML Kit for the first blink in Talking Face video

The app's results for the number of eyeblinks predicted and annotated blinks from the datasets are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. The number of eye blinks predicted by the app compared to the annotated eye blinks

Video	Number of Annotated Eyeblinks	Number of Eyeblinks Predicted by the App
EyeBlink8 #1	38	37
EyeBlink8 #2	88	88
EyeBlink8 #3	65	61
EyeBlink8 #4	31	30
EyeBlink8 #5	30	30
EyeBlink8 #6	41	41
EyeBlink8 #7	72	72
EyeBlink8 #8	43	43
Talking Face	61	61
Total	469	463

The RMSE calculated for the dataset normalized comparison with the app prediction results was 0.0654. Considering the mean RMSE results, the model effectively predicted the blinks in the reference datasets.

Table 3 compares the results from our app to those of other papers using different methods against the same datasets.

Table 3. Comparison of the results from our app to those of other papers using different methods against the same datasets

	Dataset	Precision	Recall	FP rate	Mean accuracy
Divjak & Bischof [14]	Talking	-	95.0%	19.0%	88.0%
Lee et al. [15]	Talking	83.3%	91.2%	-	-
Drutarovsky & Fogelton [6]	Talking	92.2%	96.7%	0.7%	99.0%
Our app	Talking	95.3%	100.0%	0.5%	99.6%
Drutarovsky & Fogelton [6]	EyeBlink8	79.0%	85.3%	0.7%	99.5%
Our app	EyeBlink8	84.3%	98.5%	0.8%	99.2%

The Precision metric of the EyeBlink8 dataset is lower than that of the Talking Face dataset due to a higher number of false positives (FPs). Occasionally, the app predicts partial blinks without corresponding annotated blinks in the dataset. Figure 14 illustrates a sequence of frames the app predicts as a partial blink, which are not annotated in the reference dataset, as the subject is looking down.

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Fig. 14. A sequence of frames showing a False Positive case where the app predicts a partial blink

Figure 15 displays the eye openness chart for a false positive case, where the app predicts a partial blink. The openness of both the left and right eyes falls below 0.75, indicating the onset of a partial blink. The blink concludes when the openness rises to 0.98.

Fig. 15. Eye openness chart for a case of False Positive

5 Discussion

This work presents the results of Bapp, a mobile application with machine-learning capabilities that analyzes eyelid movements in pre-recorded videos. It achieved 95.3% precision in blink detection using the Talking Face reference dataset and 84.3% using the EyeBlink8 dataset. The precision level achieved by Bapp in the Talking Face dataset is higher than the 83.3% attained by Lee et al. [15] and the 92.2% achieved by Drutarovsky and Fogelton [6]. Additionally, the precision level achieved by Bapp in the blink analysis of the EyeBlink8 dataset surpasses the 79% obtained by Drutarovsky and Fogelton [6].

Bapp's recall also exceeds that of previous works. Bapp recalled 100% of the Talking Face dataset and 98.5% of the EyeBlink8 dataset. Divjak & Bischof [14] attained a recall of 95.0% for the Talking Face dataset, while Lee et al. [15] achieved 91.2%, and

Drutarovsky and Fogelton [6] reported 96.7%. For the Eye-Blink8 dataset, Drutarovsky and Fogelton [6] reported a recall of 85.3%.

These levels of precision and recall allow Bapp to analyze eyelid movements as an alternative to manually counting blinks, primarily facilitating the monitoring of abnormal eyelid movements.

The lack of annotated datasets specifically focused on eye diseases highlights a significant gap that must be addressed. Although the existing datasets are valuable for validation, developing one that aligns more closely with the Bapp context and objectives is essential to ensure a more robust evaluation framework. For future research, I recommend utilizing datasets designed explicitly for ocular disease detection and annotated by experts in the field. That could involve creating a new dataset encompassing various ocular conditions, including blepharospasm, hemifacial spasm, ptosis, and dry eye syndrome. Collecting data under diverse lighting conditions, camera angles, and subject demographics will enhance the model's robustness.

A recent search in the electronic databases revealed only two mobile applications with eyelid movement analysis capabilities: EyeScore [12] and DryEyeRhythm [11]. We cannot find validations of these mobile applications against blink reference datasets, such as the one presented in this work, and these validations are essential for comparing the software capabilities.

Bapp can perform the analysis in a single step using only a smartphone and does not require a computer, unlike the approaches by Hu et al. [9] and Osaki et al. [2], which utilize a computer with custom software written in MATLAB for analysis. Additionally, the method by Silkiss et al. [3] involves custom software developed by a third party, Visage Technologies, to extract facial features alongside another software written in MATLAB for calculating eyelid aperture. Hedayati Amlashi et al. [10] utilized images captured at a high frame rate using a smartphone and employed Kinovea, software designed for tracking markers in human motion analysis. Silva et al. [1] developed a different approach in Python and used the Streamlit library to process the captured video through a cloud server instead of a local computer. In contrast, Bapp processes the video locally, eliminating the need to transfer data to the cloud or maintain a server. The Bapp method streamlines the operational process and allows eyelid movement analysis to reach a broader audience.

This study has limitations. One limitation is that the time required for analysis depends on several factors, including the resolution of the acquired video (the higher the resolution, the more processing time is needed) and the device used for analysis. Devices with faster processors conduct the analysis more quickly but are generally more expensive than those with slower processors, which take longer to perform the same analysis. Another significant limitation affecting the analysis's quality is the illumination conditions and camera angles from which the images were captured. Optimal results can be achieved with good lighting and the subject facing directly toward the camera in a frontal position.

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6 Conclusion

The Bapp (Blink Application) represents a significant advancement in the objective monitoring of eyelid movements and blink patterns, particularly for patients with eyelid-related diseases.

By leveraging machine learning through Google ML Kit and the Flutter platform, the application provides a unified, accessible, and multilingual solution for analyzing eyelid openness and blink detection.

Validation against publicly available datasets confirms the app's reliability and effectiveness, aligning with established methods. These results show Bapp's potential as an alternative to more resource-intensive methods using desktop computers and cloud servers.

Despite some limitations, the Bapp not only meets the need for accessible and accurate eyelid movement analysis but also provides clinicians with a practical and scalable tool to support continuous monitoring of disease progression and treatment effectiveness, thereby improving patient care. That facilitates earlier interventions and more personalized care strategies.

While some limitations remain, such as the availability and diversity of labeled training data, Bapp's success in real-world validation scenarios signals a promising future. Continued development should focus on expanding and diversifying annotated datasets, particularly those covering a wide range of ocular diseases and demographics, to further enhance diagnostic precision and clinical utility.

Overall, Bapp significantly contributes to digital ophthalmology, potentially enhancing patient engagement, remote monitoring, and clinical workflows in vision health care.

Conflict of Interest. The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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APPENDIX F

Clinically-Validated Innovative Mobile Application for Assessing Blinking and Eyelid Movements

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Abstract. Blinking is a vital physiological process that protects and maintains the health of the ocular surface. Objective assessment of eyelid movements remains challenging due to the complexity, cost, and limited clinical applicability of existing tools. This study presents the Bapp (Blink Application), a mobile application developed using the Flutter framework and integrated with Google ML Kit for on-device, real-time analysis of eyelid movements, and its clinical validation. The validation was performed using 45 videos from patients, whose blinks were manually annotated by an ophthalmology specialist as the ground truth. The Bapp's performance was evaluated using standard metrics, with results demonstrating 98.4% precision, 96.9% recall, and an overall accuracy of 98.3%. These outcomes confirm the reliability of the Bapp as a portable, accessible, and objective tool for monitoring eyelid movements. The application offers a promising alternative to traditional manual blink counting, supporting continuous ocular health monitoring and postoperative evaluation in clinical environments.

Keywords: Eyelid Movement; Blink Detection; Mobile Application; Artificial Intelligence; Clinical Validation.

1 Introduction

Eye blinking is the rapid closing and reopening of the eyelids, a spontaneous and involuntary action that preserves ocular surface health and maintains visual clarity by evenly spreading the tear film, thereby playing an essential role in protecting eye health

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and supporting visual processing [1]. Unfortunately, changes in blinking may occur in conditions such as dry eye syndrome or eyelid ptosis, or after eyelid surgery, and can potentially harm eye health [2–4].

Analyzing eyelid blinking and movement is crucial for monitoring patients with abnormal eyelid behavior. This analysis involves capturing facial images and using specialized software to recognize and measure eyelid movements [5–8]. Nevertheless, such approaches often involve complex systems that are impractical for clinical settings. Additionally, they tend to be imprecise, especially for patients with abnormal eyelid movements, and fail to capture other critical parameters, such as eyelid amplitude movements [5–8].

Fortunately, cameras, including the built-in cameras of mobile devices, can acquire images of fair quality [5–8], which, in turn, may be suitable for measuring eyelid movements using computational tools such as MATLAB [6]. Alternatively, the user would eventually rely on web-based platforms accessible on mobile devices or desktop computers to conduct these studies [5], thereby improving the applicability of these computational resources. However, despite the potential of these resources, assessing eyelid movements remains challenging due to the complexity, cost, and limited clinical applicability of existing tools.

In this work, we present a clinically-validated mobile application designed to assess eyelid movement by recording eye opening and closing over time. Validation occurred by comparing its performance against a ground truth established through frame-by-frame annotations by an ophthalmology medical specialist on a sample of patient videos. The application utilizes machine learning and computer vision tools. It offers a reliable framework for analyzing eyelid movements, providing a scalable and accessible solution for clinical and research use.

2 Related Works

Technological advancements have enhanced the analysis of eyelid blinking and movement, particularly in patient monitoring settings in which more resources are available. Also, techniques such as high-speed imaging, deep learning, and smartphone-collected videos now offer portable, accurate, and non-invasive methods for evaluating blink behavior and its connection to various eye conditions. The following works and methods reflect this evolving context.

High-speed imaging captures rapid movements at very high frame rates, enabling precise slow-motion visualization and detailed analysis of fast-moving dynamic events. When combined with digital image correlation (DIC), high-speed imaging allows accurate measurement of eyelid motion during blinking. Such a method captures detailed kinematic data—such as blink duration, eyelid displacement, and peak velocity—allowing a thorough assessment of both spontaneous and reflex blinks [9].

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Intelligent vision measurement systems powered by deep learning can analyze eye openness and provide insights into patients' visual function, especially those with dry eye disease. These systems provide information for assessing blink completeness and deliver consistent, precise measurements, improving clinical evaluations [10, 11].

Using smartphones to capture videos has proven effective for collecting raw data on eyelid movements, enabling comparative analysis of blink dynamics in patients. This approach is cost-effective and accessible, making it suitable for both clinical and research uses, as well as for initial self-assessment [12].

Few mobile applications currently provide an objective analysis of eyelid movements. Among them, DryEyeRhythm and EyeScore were developed to assess blink patterns for diagnosing dry eye. However, the latter is not available for download [13, 14]. There is no comparative validation using these apps against public datasets and clinical data.

A different method for analyzing blinks in videos involves running the application on a cloud server. Patient videos are recorded locally using a camera or smartphone and then uploaded to a web server for processing and analysis of eyelid movement. One project that adopted this method employed the Streamlit platform to host the app [5].

Although these technological advancements offer substantial benefits for tracking eyelid movement, challenges persist in standardizing these techniques across various clinical environments and promoting their widespread adoption. Additional research is necessary to confirm the effectiveness and reliability of these technologies across diverse patient groups, including individuals of different ethnicities and age ranges.

3 Proposed Method

The Bapp (Blink Application) used in this study was developed through an iterative process spanning three major versions. In the initial version [15], blink detection relied exclusively on the eye-openness probability provided by Google ML Kit. Although this approach enabled preliminary automated analysis, it was limited in distinguishing subtle or partial blinks. To address these limitations, a subsequent version was conceived, improving the algorithm's robustness by introducing multi-threshold logic and a structured decision pipeline, including pseudocode and refined criteria for blink onset and termination [16]. These refinements decreased false detections caused by probability fluctuations and enhanced temporal stability, making a key step toward a clinically usable solution.

The current, innovative version of the Bapp integrates an additional geometric indicator of eyelid separation — the Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR) — to complement the probability-based signal. EAR provides frame-by-frame information about eyelid separation, making the algorithm more sensitive to low-amplitude and incomplete blinks. This dual-signal approach enhances robustness, especially in clinical recordings where eyelid be-

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havior may deviate from standard patterns. **Fig. 1** summarizes this methodological evolution and the whole processing pipeline implemented in the present paper. It highlights the transition from the original probability-based method (v0) [15] through the threshold-based refinement (v1) [16] to the present version (v2), which incorporates the EAR-based enhancement.

Fig. 1. Consolidated flowchart showing the Bapp processing stages: video acquisition, face and eye processing (Google ML Kit), blink detection algorithm, and data export. The diagram also highlights the methodological evolution from the single-threshold approach to the multi-threshold logic and the current EAR-enhanced refinement for detecting subtle and partial blinks. The baseline version (v0) corresponds to the method introduced in [15], and the threshold-based version (v1) corresponds to the workflow presented in [16]. This work introduces EAR-based refinement to improve the detection of subtle and partial blinks.

A structured clinical validation pipeline was implemented after establishing this improved blink-detection framework. The validation relies on annotated videos by an ophthalmology specialist from the Paulista School of Medicine at the Federal University of São Paulo (EPM-UNIFESP). **Fig. 2** illustrates the validation workflow, which begins with video acquisition through Bapp. During use, the application generates a video output that isolates the eye region, enabling an ophthalmology specialist to review the footage without distraction and to precisely annotate blink events.

The specialist performs a frame-by-frame analysis of each output video, registering the start and end frames of every blink in a text file and classifying them as

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complete or partial. These annotations constitute the ground truth for evaluating the Bapp's performance.

In parallel with the visual output, the Bapp can export an Excel file containing frame-level raw data, including eye-openness probability and EAR values for each eye. These data allow a precise comparison between the signals used by the app and the events annotated by the specialist. With both datasets—annotations and raw data—available, a Python script aligns blink intervals detected by the Bapp with those marked by a specialist, identifying agreements and discrepancies.

This combined workflow, illustrated in Fig. 2, ensures that all stages—from algorithm evolution to clinical comparison—are systematically connected. It also provides the necessary information for computing the performance metrics presented in the following sections.

Fig. 2. Diagram showing the validation workflow, including the generation of annotated videos, the Bapp analysis (real-time or pre-recorded), and comparison with expert annotations.

Data collection for the clinical validation used the built-in cameras on mobile devices. The app was designed to be cross-platform, reaching nearly all Android and iOS smartphone users. In this study, the iPhone 11 and iPhone 12 (Apple Inc., Cupertino, CA) were used.

3.1 Annotated Videos

Spontaneous blinking was recorded bilaterally using the Bapp application, following previously described methods[15, 16]. All recordings were conducted with participants maintaining a primary gaze position under standardized conditions. Individuals with any eyelid, ocular surface, or neurological disorders that could influence blinking

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were excluded from the study. This study is part of a broader project previously approved by the UNIFESP Ethics Committee (CEP/UNIFESP) under the number CAAE 80417524.2.0000.5505. All participants provided written informed consent prior to their participation in the study.

The application was validated using recordings from 28 healthy adult participants, including 11 men and 17 women, aged 21 to 55 years. As several participants were evaluated more than once, the final dataset comprised 45 video samples: 25 pre-recorded and 20 collected in real time using the Bapp application. All individuals were free from ocular surface disease, neurological disorders, or eyelid abnormalities that could affect normal blink dynamics. This approach ensured that the dataset reflected physiological eyelid behavior under healthy baseline conditions and provided an appropriate reference for assessing the Bapp's performance.

The EPM-UNIFESP specialist annotates blink occurrences in the Bapp-generated output video within a text file. The footage is manually reviewed frame by frame, and the frames indicating the start and end of each blink are recorded. These annotations constitute the ground-truth data, which are then compared with the Bapp output.

Fig. 3 shows representative frame sequences from video #7 illustrating blink events: (a) depicts a complete blink, whereas (b) depicts an incomplete (partial) blink. Both events are considered blinks.

3.2 Eye Blink Detection Algorithm

The interpretation of raw data from Google ML Kit detects the frames where a blink happens. A blink starts when the eye-openness probability drops below 0.75. The blink ends when the eye-openness probability rises above 0.98.

Another method for detecting blinks relies on the EAR, which is much more sensitive. In the proposed approach, eye-openness probability serves as the primary signal for identifying complete blinks. Simultaneously, the EAR is normalized relative to its baseline open-eye value and used as a supplementary geometric indicator. A blink onset is triggered when the normalized EAR drops below 50% of its baseline, signaling a significant transient reduction in eyelid separation. This EAR-based criterion allows the detection of subtle or incomplete blinks that may not produce a significant enough change in eye-openness probability. A blink event is confirmed when either the probability thresholds are met or the EAR criterion is satisfied. **Fig. 4** shows a scenario where the EPM-UNIFESP specialist annotated a blink, but the eye-openness probability failed to detect it. **Fig. 5** displays the frame sequence corresponding to the chart in **Fig. 4**. Using EAR reduces false negatives, especially for subtle blinks.

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3.3 Blink Raw Data

The Bapp mobile application includes an export function that saves raw eye-openness probabilities and the Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR) for both eyes to an Excel file [16]. **Table 1** displays data from frames 30-45 of video #7, extracted from the Excel file generated by Bapp. The scale ranges from 0 to 1, where 0 indicates a fully closed eye and 1 indicates a fully open eye.

Fig. 3. Representative frame sequences illustrating blink events. (a) Complete blink, with full eyelid closure; (b) incomplete blink, in which eyelid closure does not reach complete occlusion.

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Fig. 4. Illustration of eye-openness probability and eye aspect ratio (EAR) normalized for a subtle blink event.

Fig. 5. Frame sequence for a subtle blink event.

Table 1. Video #7 raw blink data from Excel.

Frame	Right Eye Openness	Left Eye Openness	Right Eye EAR	Left Eye EAR
30	0.992	0.999	0.326	0.326
31	0.988	0.998	0.326	0.326
32	0.992	0.998	0.326	0.326
33	0.993	0.999	0.337	0.326

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34	0.992	0.998	0.326	0.322
35	0.993	0.691	0.236	0.225
36	0.024	0.003	0.191	0.188
37	0.029	0.001	0.189	0.200
38	0.084	0.019	0.229	0.222
39	0.994	0.987	0.275	0.255
40	0.994	0.996	0.288	0.296
41	0.995	0.998	0.324	0.304
42	0.991	0.999	0.339	0.313
43	0.993	0.998	0.335	0.328
44	0.993	0.997	0.332	0.328
45	0.993	0.997	0.339	0.326

3.4 Validation

The raw data exported from the Bapp using the Export to Excel feature were compared, for each analysis, with the annotations provided by the EPM-UNIFESP specialist. A Python script performs this validation by comparing the frame ranges in which the Bapp detects blinks with those identified by the specialist.

To accomplish the statistical calculations, the following information is generated:

- True Positive (TP): When the Bapp detects a blink and the annotations have an overlapping blink in the same frame range.
- False Positive (FP): When the Bapp detects a blink, and the annotations don't have an overlapping blink in the same frame range.
- False Negative (FN): When an annotated blink frame range doesn't have an overlapping blink detected by Bapp.
- True Negative (TN): When an open eyes range is detected by the Bapp and no blink is annotated by the EPM-UNIFESP specialist.

Fig. 6 shows a confusion matrix.

To calculate statistics from the confusion matrix data, we used the following equations:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad (1)$$

$$Recall(TP \text{ rate}) = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (2)$$

$$F1 - Score = 2 \times \frac{Precision \times Recall}{Precision+Recall} \quad (3)$$

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$$Accuracy = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \quad (4)$$

Precision measures the proportion of correct detections among all detected events. This measurement is especially relevant when the cost of a false positive—detecting a blink that did not actually occur—is high. In this context, a high-precision value indicates that the system produces very few false detections, ensuring that most identified blinks are real.

Fig. 6. Confusion matrix.

Recall measures how well the system detects all actual events, specifically genuine blinks. A high recall shows that the model finds most actual blinks, reducing missed detections. This metric is fundamental when it is unacceptable to miss any blink.

F1-Score combines precision and recall into a single balanced measure. It provides a more comprehensive assessment of the system's performance, especially when there is a trade-off between maximizing the number of detected blinks (high recall) and ensuring accurate detections (high precision).

Accuracy reflects the overall proportion of correct classifications, including both blinks and non-blinks. Although this value is high, accuracy alone can be misleading when the data are imbalanced—for instance, when there are significantly more non-blink frames than blink frames. Thus, even though it is helpful as a general indicator, it should be interpreted alongside other metrics.

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4 Results

We used 45 raw analysis datasets from 28 different individuals. The EPM-UNIFESP specialist annotated these 45 analysis-generated videos, totaling 28,975 individual frames. Fig. 7 illustrates the resulting confusion matrix, demonstrating consistently high accuracy for the derived performance metrics.

The metrics used were:

- Accuracy: 0.98361 (IC95% Wilson: 0.98208 – 0.98501)
- Precision: 0.98407 (IC95% Wilson: 0.98145 – 0.98633)
- Recall (Sensitivity/TP Rate): 0.96967 (IC95% Wilson: 0.96618 – 0.97281)
- F1-Score: 0.97682 (IC95% Bootstrap: 0.97474 – 0.97886)

These results indicate that the system is highly reliable both in correctly identifying true blink events (high recall) and in minimizing incorrect detections (high precision). To ensure statistical rigor, 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were calculated: the Wilson score interval was used for precision, recall, and accuracy, and bootstrap sampling (20,000 resamples) was used to estimate the CI for the F1-score.

Fig. 7. Confusion matrix using the complementary EAR algorithm.

Representative examples from the dataset were analyzed to better understand how these numerical results relate to real-world behavior. Several cases demonstrated the robustness of the dual-signal approach, which combines eye-openness probability with EAR. In video #11, for instance, despite poor lighting, low contrast, and visible noise, both indicators showed a clear and synchronized drop corresponding to the blink annotated by the specialist. Fig. 8 shows the sequence of frames around the blink event. Although

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the eyelid outlines are less defined and the overall image quality is poor, the eye-openness probability signal shows a clear dip at frame #22, consistent with the ground-truth annotation. **Fig. 9** presents the related chart combining eye-openness probability and EAR. Both indicators correctly identify the blink, confirming that the algorithm remains reliable even when landmark detection is more challenging due to imaging artifacts.

This example emphasizes the resilience of the Bapp's dual-signal approach (eye-openness probability + EAR), showing that the system can maintain high performance in non-ideal recording conditions—an essential requirement in real clinical settings where lighting and device quality can vary.

Fig. 8. Frame sequence from video #11 showing a blink under poor imaging conditions. Despite the low resolution, uneven illumination, and visible noise in the recording, the Bapp correctly detected the blink at frame #22.

Specific instances were examined to identify the algorithm's limitations. A small number of false-positive events occurred, usually linked to geometric fluctuations rather than misinterpretation of eyelid motion. For example, in video #12, the algorithm detected a blink at frame #6, although the specialist's annotation showed no eyelid closure. **Fig. 10** shows the EAR signals for both eyes. At frame #6, a sharp downward fluctuation crosses the blink-detection threshold, causing a false-positive. However, as shown in the frame sequence in **Fig. 11**, no actual blink occurred. The eye stays open, with no downward eyelid movement. These cases were rare and generally related to low resolution, handheld-camera instability, and slight differences in facial-landmark positioning. Since the EAR is calculated from eye-contour distances, even minor shifts between frames can falsely suggest a reduction in eyelid opening, especially in videos with motion blur or unstable focus. In this case, camera tremor caused a subtle geometric distortion mistaken for eyelid closure. Understanding these cases highlights a known

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 limitation of geometric estimators such as EAR. It underscores the potential for future use of learning-based models, which are less affected by landmark jitter.

Fig. 9. Eye-openness probability and EAR signals for video #11. Both the probability curves and EAR trajectories show a clear drop at frame #22, which aligns with the specialist annotation and confirms correct blink detection even under suboptimal video quality.

Fig. 10. This chart shows the variation of the Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR) for both eyes throughout the recording. A sharp fluctuation at frame #6 triggered a false-positive blink detection, despite no actual eyelid closure. This event illustrates how camera instability and low video resolution can introduce geometric noise, affecting EAR-based measurements.

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Fig. 11. The sequence displays the frames surrounding the false-positive event detected by the EAR algorithm. Although the system flagged frame #6 as a blink, visual inspection confirms that the eyelid remains open, indicating no blink occurred. This example demonstrates that small landmark shifts due to motion and image quality can lead to incorrect EAR-based detections.

Similarly, the system showed a few false-negative detections, usually involving very subtle partial blinks. For instance, in video #1, the specialist annotated a low-amplitude, incomplete blink between frames #131–135. However, neither the eye-opening probability nor the EAR showed enough change to exceed the detection thresholds. **Fig. 12** shows the frame sequence around the annotated interval. The blink is very subtle, with minimal eyelid displacement and no full closure. This slight movement is evident in the raw signals in **Fig. 13**. Both probability curves remain near 1.0, and the EAR values decrease only slightly around frame #133, which is insufficient to meet the algorithm's decision criteria. This example highlights a fundamental limitation of geometric methods such as EAR: very subtle eyelid movements can fall within the natural variation in landmark localization, especially when the contour shift is only a few pixels. Although these cases were rare in the dataset, they emphasize the challenge of detecting micro-blinks or low-amplitude partial blinks with threshold-based methods.

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Fig. 12. Frame sequence from video #1 illustrating a very subtle partial blink (frames #131–135). Although the specialist correctly identified the blink, the eyelid displacement is minimal, making the event visually subtle and complex for geometric estimators to capture.

Fig. 13. Eye-openness probability and EAR values for video #1. Both signals exhibit only minor fluctuations during the annotated blink interval, falling below the algorithm's detection thresholds and resulting in a false-negative event.

Taken together, the quantitative metrics and qualitative analyses show a consistent pattern: the Bapp performs reliably across a wide range of real-world conditions, whereas the few remaining detection errors can be attributed to well-defined boundary cases such as unstable recordings or very low-amplitude eyelid movements.

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5 Discussion

The results of this study show that the Bapp, by combining eye-openness probability and EAR, provides reliable, clinically meaningful blink detection in real-world recording environments. As a cross-platform mobile application compatible with both Android and iOS devices, equipped with machine-learning capabilities that analyze eyelid movements in pre-recorded videos and in real time, the Bapp offers broad accessibility and practical utility in clinical and research settings. The system's high precision (98.4%) and recall (96.9%) confirm its ability to accurately detect actual blink events while minimizing false positives, even when videos are captured under diversified lighting conditions, with varying camera stability, or at different camera angles. The precision achieved by the Bapp in previous analyses on public datasets was 95.3% on the Talking Face and 84.3% on the EyeBlink8 dataset [16]. These precision levels enable the Bapp to analyze eyelid movements rather than relying on manual blink counting, thereby facilitating the monitoring of abnormal eyelid activity.

Additionally, the qualitative analysis of individual cases offers valuable insights into the behavior of the current detection framework. As shown in the Results section, the EAR-enhanced algorithm demonstrated both strengths and limitations under challenging conditions. A representative false-positive case occurred in a low-resolution, unstable video, where camera motion caused geometric distortions that briefly made the EAR appear to mimic eyelid closure. In contrast, another example showed that the system remains highly reliable even in poor lighting and noisy conditions, accurately identifying a blink despite low-quality images. A false-negative case illustrated the difficulty of detecting extremely subtle, low-amplitude blinks: the eyelid movement was so slight that neither the eye-openness probability nor the EAR showed a sufficiently distinct change to exceed detection thresholds. These examples highlight the boundary conditions of the probability- and EAR-based approach and help contextualize the quantitative results presented earlier.

A key feature of this study's clinical data collection is the absence of standardization in specific capture parameters, especially lighting conditions and camera angles. While sources suggest optimal results require proper lighting and the subject facing directly toward a stable frontal camera, the present study's validation used 45 videos from patients in environments with diverse illumination. The high performance—98.4% precision and 96.9% recall—despite these variations in real clinical environments—shows the robustness of the Bapp model for analyzing eyelid movement. Using videos with annotations provided by an EPM-UNIFESP specialist in clinical settings enables validation with a more diverse dataset.

The primary limitation of the present work concerns the duration of the analytical process, which depends on multiple factors, including the resolution of the recorded video and the device's computational power. Furthermore, the type of smartphone used

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for real-time analysis also affects processing performance. Devices with slower processors may experience increased latency or reduced frame consistency, while high-end devices execute the analysis more smoothly. Higher video resolutions require longer processing times, while devices with faster processors can complete the analysis more quickly. However, such devices are generally more expensive than those with slower processors, which take more time to perform the same tasks. Although these differences do not reflect limitations of the algorithm itself, they highlight the dependence of real-time performance on the user's hardware.

Additionally, the original recordings can vary in overall image quality due to differences in smartphone hardware, lens properties, and internal image-processing pipelines. These factors can affect the reliability of eyelid landmark detection and cause fluctuations in the stability of eye-openness and EAR measurements. Modern smartphones use automatic illumination compensation, exposure correction, and noise-reduction algorithms, which may cause frame-to-frame pixel variations and affect the stability of blink-related features. Camera stability also plays a key role; therefore, using a suitable mounting system would mitigate motion artifacts.

Looking forward, several improvements could affect the system's reliability. Using deep learning models that learn spatiotemporal features of eyelid motion may reduce reliance on geometric thresholds and improve the detection of micro- and partial blinks. Additional refinements in stabilization, landmark filtering, or adaptive thresholding could mitigate the effects of camera movement and facial landmark jitter. The platform also presents opportunities to integrate into telemedicine workflows, allowing remote monitoring of patients with ocular surface diseases, facial nerve issues, or post-surgical conditions.

The Bapp's portability, multiplatform availability, and ability to perform both real-time and offline analyses make it a promising tool not only for point-in-time evaluations but also for long-term monitoring. These features enable the application to track blink dynamics over time and assess treatment responses—such as evaluating the effects of botulinum toxin in patients with facial movement disorders or monitoring outcomes in dry eye therapy. Such use cases further emphasize the clinical importance of a reliable, accessible, and automated blink-assessment tool.

To fully establish the Bapp's generalizability, future work should include validation across larger, more diverse populations spanning a wider range of ages, ethnicities, eyelid shapes, and clinical conditions. Expanding the dataset in this way will be essential to confirm the system's robustness and ensure its suitability for various ophthalmic and neurological contexts.

Overall, the results show that the Bapp is a strong, easy-to-use, and clinically relevant tool for automated blink analysis in many real-world recording scenarios. These features make the mobile application a promising option for long-term monitoring, research, and future clinical use.

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6 Conclusion

The Bapp application successfully passed clinical validation through annotations performed by an ophthalmology specialist on real patient videos, demonstrating reliable and objective detection of eyelid movements. The system achieved 98.4% precision and 96.9% recall, confirming its high accuracy and robustness in detecting blinks. These results strengthen the Bapp's potential as a portable, accessible, and multilingual tool for continuous patient monitoring and postoperative assessment.

7 Disclosure statement

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

8 Author contributions

Gustavo Adolpho Bonesso: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, review & editing.

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9 Funding

This work was developed using resources obtained from the São Paulo Research Foundation (FAPESP) [grant numbers 2017/22949-3 and 2012/01505-6].

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